

The Human Gene Project

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Preface

The Human Gene Project was a groundbreaking scientific initiative aimed at mapping and understanding all the genes in the human genome its sought to identify the functions of genes, and explore how they contribute to health and disease.

chromosome 1

p-arm

- AADACL3: Arylacetamide deacetylase-like 3
- AADACL4: Arylacetamide deacetylase-like 4
- ACADM: acyl-Coenzyme A dehydrogenase, C-4 to C-12 straight chain
- ACTG1P6: encoding protein Actin, gamma 1 pseudogene 6
- ACTL8: Actin-like 8
- ADGRL2 (1p31.1): adhesion G protein-coupled receptor L2
- ADPRHL2: Poly(ADP-ribose) glycohydrolase ARH3
- AMPD2: encoding enzyme AMP deaminase 2
- ARID1A (1p36)
- ATXN7L2: Ataxin 7-like 2
- AZIN2: encoding enzyme Antizyme inhibitor 2 (AzI2) also known as arginine decarboxylase (ADC)
- BCAS2: Breast carcinoma amplified sequence 2
- BCL10 (1p22)
- LRIF1: encoding protein Ligand-dependent nuclear receptor-interacting factor 1
- C1orf109: chromosome 1 open reading frame 109
- C1orf162: encoding protein Chromosome 1 open reading frame 162
- C1orf194: encoding protein Chromosome 1 open reading frame 194
- CZIB: chromosome 1 open reading frame 123
- CACHD1 encoding protein Cache domain containing 1
- CAMK2N1: encoding protein Calcium/calmodulin dependent protein kinase II inhibitor 1
- CAMTA1 (1p36)
- CASP9 (1p36)
- CASZ1 (1p36): Castor zinc finger 1
- CCDC17: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 17
- CCDC18: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 18
- CEP85: encoding protein Centrosomal protein 85
- CFAP74: encoding protein Cilia and flagella associated protein 74
- CHD5 (1p36)
- CLIC4 (1p36)
- CLSPN (1p34)
- CMPK: UMP-CMP kinase
- COL16A1 (1p35)
- COL11A1: collagen, type XI, alpha 1
- CPT2: carnitine palmitoyltransferase II
- CRYZ: Crystallin zeta
- CSDE1: Cold shock domain containing E1

- CYP4B1 (1p33)
- CYR61 (1p22)
- DBT: dihydrolipoamide branched chain transacylase E2
- DCLRE1B: DNA cross-link repair 1B
- DEPDC1 encoding protein DEP domain containing 1
- DIRAS3 (1p31): DIRAS family, GTP-binding RAS-like 3
- DISP3: encoding protein Dispatched rnd transporter family member 3
- DNASE2B: encoding protein Deoxyribonuclease 2 beta
- DPH5: Diphthine synthase
- DVL1 (1p36)
- ENO1 (1p36)
- EPHA2 (1p36)
- EPS15 (1p32)
- ESPN: espin (autosomal recessive deafness 36)
- EVI5: ecotropic viral integration site 5
- EXO5: encoding protein Exonuclease 5
- EXTL1: exostosin like glycosyltransferase 1
- EXTL2: exostosin like glycosyltransferase 2
- FAM46B: family with sequence similarity 46, member B
- FAM46C: family with sequence similarity 46, member C
- FAM76A: family with sequence similarity 76, member A
- FAM87B: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 87 member B
- FBXO2: F-box protein 2
- FNBP1L encoding protein Formin-binding protein 1-like
- FPGT: Fucose-1-phosphate guanylyltransferase
- FUBP1 (1p31)
- GALE: UDP-galactose-4-epimerase
- GADD45A (1p31)
- GBP1 (1p22)
- GBP2: guanylate binding protein 2
- GBP5 encoding protein Guanylate binding protein 5
- GBP6: encoding protein Guanylate binding protein family member 6
- GJB3: gap junction protein, beta 3, 31kDa (connexin 31)
- GLMN (1p22)
- GNL2: G protein nucleolar 2
- GSTM1 (1p13)
- GUCA2B: encoding protein Guanylate cyclase activator 2B
- HDAC1 (1p35)
- HES2: Hes family bHLH transcription factor 2
- HES3: Hes family bHLH transcription factor 3
- HMGCL: 3-hydroxymethyl-3-methylglutaryl-Coenzyme A lyase (hydroxymethylglutaricaciduria)
- HAO2 encoding protein Hydroxyacid oxidase 2
- HMGCS2: 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-CoA synthase 2
- HP1BP3: Heterochromatin protein 1, binding protein 3

- IFI6: Interferon alpha-inducible protein 6
- IL22RA1 (1p36)
- INTS11: Integrator complex subunit 11
- JAK1 (1p31)
- JUN (1p32)
- KANK4: encoding protein KN motif and ankyrin repeat domains 4
- KCNQ4: potassium voltage-gated channel, KQT-like subfamily, member 4
- KIF1B: kinesin family member 1B
- L1TD1: LINE-1 type transposase domain containing 1
- LCK (1p35)
- LINC01137: encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1137
- LRRC39: Leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 39
- LRRC40: Leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 40
- LRRC41: Leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 41
- LRRC8D: Leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 8D
- MACO1: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 57
- MAN1A2: Mannosyl-oligosaccharide 1,2-alpha-mannosidase IB
- MAP3K6: encoding protein Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 6
- MEAF6: MYST/ESA1 associated factor 6
- MECR: Trans-2-enoyl-CoA reductase, mitochondrial
- MFAP2: Microfibrillar-associated protein 2
- MIB2 (1p36)
- MIER1 (1p31)
- MIGA1: encoding protein Mitoguardin 1
- MFN2: mitofusin 2
- MFSD2: Major facilitator superfamily domain containing 2A
- MIR6079: microRNA 6079
- MMEL1: Membrane metallo-endopeptidase-like 1
- MTFR1L: mitochondrial fission regulator 1 like
- MTHFR (1p36): 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (NADPH)
- MUL1: Mitochondrial E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 1
- MUTYH (1p34): mutY homolog (E. coli)
- NBPF3: Neuroblastoma breakpoint family member 3
- NDUFA4P1: encoding protein Nadh dehydrogenase (ubiquinone) 1 alpha subcomplex, 4, 9kda, pseudogene 1
- NGF: Nerve Growth Factor
- NOL9: Nucleolar protein 9
- NRAS (1p13)
- NOTCH2 (1p12)
- OLFML3: Olfactomedin-like 3
- OMA1: Metalloendopeptidase OMA1, mitochondrial
- OVGP1: Oviductal glycoprotein 1
- PARK7 (1p36): Parkinson disease (autosomal recessive, early onset) 7
- PINK1: PTEN induced putative kinase 1
- PLOD1: procollagen-lysine 1, 2-oxoglutarate 5-dioxygenase 1

- PRAMEF10: encoding protein Prame family member 10
- PRMT6: Protein arginine methyltransferase 6
- PRXL2B: encoding protein Peroxiredoxin like 2B
- PSRC1: Proline/serine-rich coiled-coil protein 1
- RAD54L: RAD54-like
- RAP1A (1p13)
- RBM15 (1p13)
- RCC2: Regulator of chromosome condensation 2
- REG4 (1p12)
- RHBDL2: Rhomboid like 2
- RHOC (1p13)
- RIMS3: encoding protein Regulating synaptic membrane exocytosis 3
- RLF: rearranged L-myc fusion
- RNF11 (1p32)
- RNF19B: encoding protein Ring finger protein 19B
- RNF220: RING finger protein 220
- RPA2 (1p35)
- RSPO1 (1p34)
- S100A1 (1q21)
- SAMD11: encoding protein Sterile alpha motif domain containing 11
- SDC3: Syndecan-3
- SDHB (1p36)
- SFPQ (1p34): encoding protein Splicing factor proline and glutamine rich
- SGIP1: SH3 domain GRB2-like protein 3-interaction protein 1
- SH3BGRL3: SH3 domain-binding glutamic acid-rich-like protein 3
- SLC16A1 (1p13)
- SLC2A1 Glucose transporter 1
- SPSB1: SPRY domain-containing SOCS box protein 1
- STIL (1p33)
- SYCP1: Synaptonemal complex protein 1
- SZT2: Seizure threshold 2 homolog
- TACSTD2: tumor-associated calcium signal transducer 2
- TAL1 (1p33)
- TCTEX1D4: encoding protein Tctex1 domain containing 4
- TCEB3: Transcription elongation factor B polypeptide 3
- TGFBR3 (1p22)
- THRAP3 (1p34)
- TIE1 (1p34)
- TM2D1: encoding protein Tm2 domain containing 1
- TMCO2: encoding protein transmembrane and coiled-coil domains 2
- TMCO4: encoding protein transmembrane and coiled-coil domains 4
- TMEM48: encoding protein nucleoporin NDC1
- TMEM50A: Transmembrane protein 50A
- TMEM59: Transmembrane protein 59

- TMEM69: Transmembrane protein 69
- TMEM201 encoding protein Transmembrane protein 201
- TMEM222: Transmembrane protein 222
- TOE1: Target of EGR1 protein 1
- TRABD2B: encoding protein Trab domain containing 2b
- TRAPPC3: Trafficking protein particle complex subunit 3
- TRIT1: tRNA isopentenyltransferase, mitochondrial
- TSHB: thyroid stimulating hormone, beta
- TTC39A: Tetratricopeptide repeat 39A
- UBR4: E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase component n-recognin 4
- UROD: uroporphyrinogen decarboxylase (the gene for porphyria cutanea tarda)
- USP1 (1p31)
- USP48: Ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase 48
- VAV3 (1p13)
- VPS13D: Vacuolar protein sorting-associated protein 13D
- VTCN1 (1p13)
- WARS2: Tryptophanyl-tRNA synthetase, mitochondrial
- WDR77 (1p13)
- YBX1 (1p34)
- ZCCHC17: zinc finger CCHC-type containing 17
- ZFP69: encoding protein Zfp69 zinc finger protein
- ZMYM1 encoding protein Zinc finger MYM-type containing 1
- ZNF436: Zinc finger protein 436
- ZNF684: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 684
- ZYG11B encoding protein Zyg-11 family member B, cell cycle regulator
- ZZZ3: ZZ-type zinc finger-containing protein 3

q-arm

Partial list of the genes located on q-arm (long arm) of human chromosome 1:

- ABL2 (1q25)
- ADIPOR1 (1q32)
- AHCTF1: encoding protein ELYS
- AKT3 (1q43-44)
- ANGPTL1: Angiopoietin-related protein 1
- ARHGEF2 (1q22)
- ARID4B: encoding protein AT-rich interactive domain-containing protein 4B
- ARV1 encoding protein ARV1 homolog (*S. cerevisiae*)
- ARNT (1q21)
- ASPM (1q31): a brain size determinant
- ATF3 (1q32)
- ATP2B4 (1q32)
- BCL9 (1q21)
- CATSPERE: encoding protein Catsper channel auxiliary subunit epsilon

- C1orf21: chromosome 1 open reading frame 21
- MMTAP2 encoding protein Multiple myeloma tumor-associated protein 2
- TEX35: TEX35
- C1orf74: chromosome 1 open reading frame 74
- C2CD4D: C2 calcium-dependent domain-containing 4D
- CTSS: Cathepsin S
- CD5L: CD5 molecule like
- CENPL: Centromere protein L
- CENPF (1q41)
- CHTOP: Chromatin target of prmt1
- CNIH4: cornichon homolog 4
- CNST: Consortin
- CREG1: Cellular repressor of E1A stimulated genes 1
- CRP: C-reactive protein
- CRTC2 (1q21)
- CSRP1: Cysteine and glycine rich protein 1
- DCAF8: encoding protein DDB1 and CUL4 associated factor 8
- DDX59: DEAD-box helicase 59
- DEL1Q21: encoding protein Chromosome 1q21.1 deletion syndrome
- DPT: Dermatopontin
- DISC2, long non-coding RNA
- DNAH14 encoding protein Dynein, axonemal, heavy chain 14
- DUSP10 (1q41)
- DUSP27: encoding protein Dual specificity phosphatase 27 (putative)
- ECM1 (1q21)
- EDEM3: ER degradation enhancing alpha-mannosidase like protein 3
- EGLN1 (1q42)
- ELF3: encoding protein E74 like ets transcription factor 3
- ENAH (1q42)
- ESRRG (1q41)
- FAM129A: family with sequence similarity 129, member A
- FAM163A: encoding protein neuroblastoma-derived secretory protein
- FAM20B: FAM20B, glycosaminoglycan xylosylkinase
- FAM63A: Family with sequence similarity 63, member A
- FAM78B: family with sequence similarity 78, member B
- FAM89A: encoding protein Fam89A
- FBXO28: F-box protein 28
- FCMR: Fc fragment of IgM receptor
- FCGR2B (1q23)
- FCGR2C: encoding protein Fc fragment of igg receptor iic (gene/pseudogene)
- FH (1q43): fumarase
- FLAD1: encoding protein Flavin adenine dinucleotide synthetase 1
- FLG-AS1: encoding protein FLG antisense RNA 1
- FMO3: flavin containing monooxygenase 3

- FRA1J encoding protein Fragile site, 5-azacytidine type, common, fra(1)(q12)
- G0S2: encoding G0/G1 switch 2
- GAS5 (1q25)
- GBA: glucosidase, beta; acid (includes glucosylceramidase) (gene for Gaucher disease)
- GBAP1: glucosylceramidase beta pseudogene 1
- GLC1A: gene for glaucoma
- GON4L: gon-4 like
- GPA33 (1q24)
- GPR37L1 G protein-coupled receptor 37 like 1
- H3C13: encoding protein Histone cluster 2 h3 family member d
- HEATR1: HEAT repeat-containing protein 1
- HFE2: hemochromatosis type 2 (juvenile)
- HIST2H2AB: Histone 2A type 2-B
- HIST2H2BF: Histone H2B type 2-F
- HIST2H3PS2: Histone cluster 2, H3, pseudogene 2
- HIST3H2A: Histone H2A type 3
- HIST3H2BB: Histone H2B type 3-B
- HRM2: Hair, curly
- IGSF8 (1q23)
- INAVA: Innate immunity activator protein
- INTS3: Integrator complex subunit 3
- IRF2BP2: encoding protein Interferon regulatory factor 2 binding protein 2
- IRF6: gene for connective tissue formation
- KCNH1 (1q32)
- KIF14 (1q32)
- LEFTY1: Left-right determination factor 1
- LHX9 encoding protein LIM homeobox 9
- LMNA: lamin A/C
- LMOD1: encoding protein Leiomodin 1
- LOC645166 encoding protein Lymphocyte-specific protein 1 pseudogene
- LYPLAL1: Lysophospholipase-like 1
- MAPKAPK2 (1q32)
- MIR194-1: microRNA 194-1
- MIR5008: microRNA 5008
- MPC2: Mitochondrial pyruvate carrier 2
- MOSC1: MOCO sulphurase C-terminal domain containing 1
- MOSC2: MOSC domain-containing protein 2, mitochondrial
- MPZ: myelin protein zero (Charcot–Marie–Tooth neuropathy 1B)
- MSTO1: misato 1
- MTR: 5-methyltetrahydrofolate-homocysteine methyltransferase
- NAV1: Neuron navigator 1
- NBPF16: Neuroblastoma breakpoint family, member 16
- NOC2L: Nucleolar complex protein 2 homolog
- NUCKS1: Nuclear ubiquitous casein and cyclin-dependent kinases substrate

- NVL: Nuclear valosin-containing protein-like
- OLFML2B: Olfactomedin-like 2B
- OPTC: Opticin
- OTUD7B: OTU domain-containing protein 7B
- PACERR encoding protein PTGS2 antisense NFKB1 complex-mediated expression regulator RNA
- PBX1 (1q23)
- PEA15 (1q23)
- PGDB5: PiggyBac transposable element derived 5
- PIAS3 (1q21)
- P4KB: Phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase beta
- PIP5K1A (1q21): Phosphatidylinositol-4-phosphate 5-kinase type-1 alpha
- PLA2G4A (1q31)
- PPOX: protoporphyrinogen oxidase
- PRCC (1q23)
- PRR9 encoding protein Proline rich 9
- PSEN2 (1q42): presenilin 2 (Alzheimer disease 4)
- PTGS2 (1q31)
- PTPN14 (1q32-41)
- PTPN7 (1q32)
- RABIF: RAB interacting factor
- RASSF5 (1q32)
- RGS2 (1q31)
- RN5S1@: RNA, 5S ribosomal 1q42 cluster
- RPS27 (1q21)
- SCAMP3: Secretory carrier-associated membrane protein 3
- SDHC (1q23)
- SELE (1q24)
- SFT2D2: encoding protein Sft2 domain containing 2
- SHC1 (1q21)
- SHCBP1L: encoding protein Shc binding and spindle associated 1 like
- SLC30A10: encoding protein Solute carrier family 30 member 10
- SLC39A1 (1q21)
- SLC50A1: Solute carrier family 50 member 1
- SMCP: Sperm mitochondrial-associated cysteine-rich protein
- SMG7: nonsense mediated mRNA decay factor
- SMYD3 (1q44)
- SPG23
- SPRR1A: Cornifin-A
- SPRR1B: Cornifin-B
- SPRR2A: Small proline rich protein 2A
- SPRTN: Spartan
- TARBP1: TAR (HIV-1) RNA-binding protein 1
- TBCE: Tubulin-specific chaperone E
- THBS3: Thrombospondin 3

- TMCO1: Transmembrane and coiled-coil domain-containing protein 1
- TMEM9: Transmembrane protein 9
- TMEM63A: Transmembrane protein 63A
- TMEM81: Transmembrane protein 81
- TNFAIP8L2: encoding TNF alpha induced protein 8 like 2
- TNFSF18 (1q25)
- TNNT2: cardiac troponin T2
- TOR1AIP1: Torsin-1A-interacting protein 1
- TOR3A: encoding protein Torsin family 3 member A
- TP53BP2 (1q41)
- TRE-CTC1-5: Transfer RNA-Glu (CTC) 1-5
- UAP1: UDP-N-acetylhexosamine pyrophosphorylase
- USH2A: Usher syndrome 2A (autosomal recessive, mild)
- USF1 (1q23)
- VANGL2: encoding protein VANGL planar cell polarity protein 2
- VPS45: Vacuolar protein sorting-associated protein 45
- VPS72: Vacuolar protein sorting-associated protein 72
- YY1AP1: YY1-associated protein 1
- ZBED6: zinc finger, BED-type containing 6
- ZC3H11A: Zinc finger CCCH domain-containing protein 11A
- ZNF648 encoding protein Zinc finger protein 648
- ZNF669: Zinc finger protein 669
- ZNF687: Zinc finger protein 687
- ZNF692: Zinc finger protein 692
- ZNF695: Zinc finger protein 695

Diseases and disorders

- 1q21.1 deletion syndrome
- 1q21.1 duplication syndrome
- Alzheimer's disease
- Autosomal dominant Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease type 2 with giant axons
- Bipolar disorder
- Breast cancer
- Brooke Greenberg Disease (Syndrome X)
- Carnitine palmitoyltransferase II deficiency
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease, types 1 and 2
- collagenopathy, types II and XI
- congenital hypothyroidism

chromosome 2

List of genes

p-arm

- ACTR2: encoding protein Actin-related protein 2
- ADI1: encoding enzyme 1,2-dihydroxy-3-keto-5-methylthiopentene dioxygenase
- AFF3: encoding protein AF4/FMR2 family member 3
- AFTPH: encoding protein Aftiphilin
- ALMS1: Alstrom syndrome 1
- ABCG5 and ABCG8: ATP-binding cassette, subfamily A, members 5 and 8
- ASXL2: Additional sex combs like 2, transcriptional regulator
- ATOH8: encoding protein Atonal bHLH transcription factor 8
- ATRAID: encoding protein Apoptosis-related protein 3
- BCYRN1: BC200 lncRNA
- C2orf16: unknown protein C2orf16
- CAPG: capping acting protein
- CCDC104: Coiled-coil domain containing 104
- CCDC142: Coiled-coil domain containing 142
- CCDC142: Coiled-Coil Domain Containing 142
- CGREF1: encoding protein Cell growth regulator with EF-hand domain 1
- CLEC4F: encoding protein C-type lectin domain family 4 member F
- CTLA4: cytotoxic T-Lymphocyte Antigen 4
- CYTOR: Cytoskeleton regulator RNA
- DHX57: DExH-box helicase 57
- DPYSL5: Dihydropyrimidinase like 5
- ERLEC1: Endoplasmic reticulum lectin 1
- EVA1A: encoding protein Eva-1 homolog A (C. elegans)
- EXOC6B: encoding protein Exocyst complex component 6b
- FAM49A: Family with sequence similarity 49 member A

- FAM98A: Family with sequence similarity 98 member A
- FAM136A: Family with sequence similarity 136 member A
- FBXO11: F-box protein 11
- FTH1P3: encoding protein Ferritin heavy chain 1 pseudogene 3
- GEN1 encoding protein GEN1, Holliday junction 5' flap endonuclease
- GCKR: Glucokinase regulator
- GFPT1: glutamine—fructose-6-phosphate transaminase 1
- GKN1: gastroke 1
- GPATCH11: G-patch domain containing protein 11
- GTF2A1L: General transcription factor IIA subunit 1 like
- HADHA: hydroxyacyl-Coenzyme A dehydrogenase/3-ketoacyl-Coenzyme A thiolase/enoyl-Coenzyme A hydratase (trifunctional protein), alpha subunit
- HADHB: hydroxyacyl-Coenzyme A dehydrogenase/3-ketoacyl-Coenzyme A thiolase/enoyl-Coenzyme A hydratase (trifunctional protein), beta subunit
- HSPC159: Galectin-related protein
- ID2-AS1: encoding protein Id2 antisense rna 1 (head to head)
- LCLAT1: encoding protein Lysocardiolipin acyltransferase 1
- LEPQTL1: Leptin, serum levels of
- MBOAT2: encoding protein Membrane bound o-acyltransferase domain containing 2
- MEMO1: Mediator of cell motility 1
- MPHOSPH10: M-phase phosphoprotein 10
- MSH2: mutS homolog 2, colon cancer, nonpolyposis type 1 (*E. coli*)
- MSH6: mutS homolog 6 (*E. coli*)
- MTHFD2: Bifunctional methylenetetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase/cyclohydrolase, mitochondrial
- MTIF2: mitochondrial translational initiation factor 2
- NDUFAF7: Protein arginine methyltransferase NDUFAF7, mitochondrial
- NRBP1: Nuclear receptor-binding protein 1
- ODC1: Ornithine decarboxylase
- OTOF: otoferlin
- PAIP2B: Poly(a) binding protein interacting protein 2b
- PARK3 encoding protein Parkinson disease 3 (autosomal dominant, Lewy body)
- PCBP1-AS1: encoding protein PCBP1 antisense RNA 1
- PCYOX1: prenylcysteine oxidase 1
- PELI1: Ubiquitin ligase
- PLGLB2: Plasminogen-related protein B
- POLR1A: DNA-directed RNA polymerase I subunit RPA1
- PREPL: Prolyl endopeptidase-like
- PXDN: Peroxidasin homolog
- QPCT: Glutaminy-peptide cyclotransferase
- RETSAT: All-trans-retinol 13,14-reductase
- RNF103: encoding protein Ring finger protein 103
- RNF103-CHMP3: encoding protein RNF103-CHMP3 readthrough
- SH3YL1: SH3 and SYLF domain-containing 1
- SLC35F6: encoding protein Transmembrane protein SLC35F6

- TGOLN2: Trans-Golgi network integral membrane protein 2
- THADA: encoding protein Thyroid adenoma associated
- TIA1: TIA1 cytotoxic granule-associated RNA binding protein
- TMEM150: Transmembrane protein 150A
- TP53I3: Putative quinone oxidoreductase
- TPO: thyroid peroxidase
- TTC7A: familial multiple intestinal atresia
- WBP1: WW domain-binding protein 1
- WDCP: WD Repeat and Coiled Coil Containing Protein
- WDPCP: encoding protein Wd repeat containing planar cell polarity effector

q-arm

Partial list of the genes located on q-arm (long arm) of human chromosome 2:

- ABCA12: ATP-binding cassette, subfamily A (ABC1), member 12
- ACTR1B: encoding protein Beta-actin
- AGXT: alanine-glyoxylate aminotransferase (oxalosis I; hyperoxaluria I; glycolicaciduria; serine-pyruvate aminotransferase)
- ALS2: amyotrophic lateral sclerosis 2 (juvenile)
- ALS2CR8: encoding protein Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis 2 chromosomal region candidate gene 8 protein also known as calcium-response factor (CaRF)
- ARMC9: encoding protein LisH domain-containing protein ARMC9
- B3GNT7: encoding protein UDP-GlcNAc:betaGal beta-1,3-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase 7
- BCS1L: GRACILE (Finnish heritage disease) related gene
- BMPR2: bone morphogenetic protein receptor, type II (serine/threonine kinase)
- C2orf40: encoding protein Augurin
- C2orf54: Chromosome 2 open reading frame 54
- CCDC115: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 115
- CCDC138: Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 138
- CCDC74A: Coiled-coil domain containing 74a
- CCDC88A: Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 88A
- CCDC93: Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 93
- CDCA7: Cell division cycle associated protein 1
- CHPF: Chondroitin sulfate synthase 2
- CKAP2L: encoding protein Cytoskeleton associated protein 2 like
- COL3A1: collagen, type III, alpha 1 (Ehlers-Danlos syndrome type IV, autosomal dominant)
- COL4A3: collagen, type IV, alpha 3 (Goodpasture antigen)
- COL4A4: collagen, type IV, alpha 4
- COL5A2: collagen, type V, alpha 2
- DES: Desmin protein
- DIS3L2: DIS3 mitotic control homolog-like 2
- ECEL1: Endothelin converting enzyme like 1
- EPC2: Enhancer of polycomb homolog 2
- EPB41L5: encoding protein Erythrocyte membrane protein band 4.1 like 5

- ERICH2: encoding protein Glutamate rich protein 2
- FASTKD1: FAST kinase domain-containing protein 1
- IMP4: U3 small nucleolar ribonucleoprotein
- INPP1: Inositol polyphosphate 1-phosphatase
- INPP4A: inositol polyphosphate-4-phosphatase type A
- ITM2C: Integral membrane protein 2C
- KANSL3: KAT8 regulatory NSL complex subunit 3
- KIAA1211L: Uncharacterized Protein KIAA1211- Like
- LANCL1: LanC like 1
- LINC00607: Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 607
- LOC100287387: LOC100287387
- MALL: MAL-like protein
- MBD5: encoding protein Methyl-cpg binding domain protein 5
- MFSD2B: encoding protein Major facilitator superfamily domain containing 2b
- MGAT5: mannosyl (alpha-1,6-)-glycoprotein beta-1,6-N-acetyl-glucosaminyltransferase
- MIR375: encoding protein MicroRNA 375
- MIR561: encoding protein MicroRNA 561
- NABP1: Nucleic acid binding protein 1
- NEURL3: encoding protein Neuralized E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 3
- NCL: Nucleolin
- NR4A2: nuclear receptor subfamily 4, group A, member 2
- OLA1: Obg-like ATPase 1
- PARD3B encoding protein Partitioning defective 3 homolog B
- PAX3: paired box gene 3 (Waardenburg syndrome 1)
- PAX8: paired box gene 8
- PID1: Phosphotyrosine interaction domain containing 1
- POLR1B: DNA-directed RNA polymerase I subunit RPA2
- PRR21: Proline-rich protein 21
- PRSS56: Putative serine protease 56
- RBM44: Rna binding motif protein 44
- RFX8: Rfx family member 8, lacking rfx dna binding domain
- RIF1: replication timing regulatory factor 1
- RNU4ATAC: RNA, U4atac small nuclear (U12-dependent splicing)
- RPL37A: encoding protein 60S ribosomal protein L37a
- SATB2: Homeobox 2
- SCARNA5: Small Cajal body-specific RNA 5
- SDPR: Serum deprivation-response protein
- SGOL2: Shugoshin-like 2
- SH3BP4: SH3 domain-binding protein 4
- SLC9A4: solute carrier family 9 member A4
- SLC40A1: solute carrier family 40 (iron-regulated transporter), member 1
- SMPD4: Sphingomyelin phosphodiesterase 4
- SP140: encoding protein SP140 nuclear body protein
- SP140L: encoding protein Sp140 nuclear body protein like

- **SPATS2L**: spermatogenesis associated, serine-rich 2-like protein
- **SSB**: Sjögren syndrome antigen B
- **SSFA2**: Sperm-specific antigen 2
- **STK11IP**: encoding protein Serine/threonine kinase 11 interacting protein
- **TBR1**: T-box, brain, 1
- **THAP4**: THAP domain-containing protein 4
- **TMBIM1**: Transmembrane BAX inhibitor motif-containing protein 1
- **TMEM182**: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 182
- **TNRC15**: PERQ amino acid-rich with GYF domain-containing protein 2
- **TSGA10** encoding protein Testis specific 10
- **TTN**: titin
- **TUBA4B**: encoding protein Tubulin alpha 4b
- **UBE2F**: encoding protein Ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2 F (putative)
- **UBXD2**: UBX domain-containing protein 4
- **UXS1**: UDP-glucuronic acid decarboxylase 1
- **VIL1**: encoding protein Villin 1
- **XIRP2**: Xin actin-binding repeat-containing protein 2
- **ZEB2-AS1**: encoding protein ZEB2-AS1
- **ZNF142**: zinc finger protein 142
- **ZNF2**: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 2

Related disorders and traits

- 2p15-16.1 microdeletion syndrome
- Autism
- Alport syndrome
- Alström syndrome
- Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
- Brachydactyly type D
- Cleft chin
- Congenital hypothyroidism
- Crigler–Najjar syndrome types I/II
- Dementia with Lewy bodies
- Ehlers–Danlos syndrome
- Ehlers–Danlos syndrome, classical type
- Ehlers–Danlos syndrome, vascular type
- Fibrodysplasia ossificans progressiva
- Gilbert's syndrome
- Harlequin-type ichthyosis
- Hemochromatosis
- Hemochromatosis type 4
- Hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer
- Infantile-onset ascending hereditary spastic paralysis
- Juvenile primary lateral sclerosis
- Lactose intolerance
- Long-chain 3-hydroxyacyl-coenzyme A dehydrogenase deficiency
- Lowry-Wood syndrome
- Maturity-onset diabetes of the young type 6
- Mitochondrial trifunctional protein deficiency
- Nonsyndromic deafness
- Photoc sneeze reflex
- Primary hyperoxaluria
- Primary pulmonary hypertension
- Sitosterolemia (knockout of either ABCG5 or ABCG8)
- Sensenbrenner syndrome
- Synesthesia
- Waardenburg syndrome

chromosome 3

List of genes

p-arm

- ALAS1: aminolevulinate, delta-, synthase 1
- APEH: encoding enzyme Acylamino-acid-releasing enzyme
- ARPP-21: Cyclic AMP-regulated phosphoprotein, 21 kDa
- AZI2: encoding protein 5-azacytidine-induced protein 2
- BRK1: SCAR/WAVE actin nucleating complex subunit
- BRPF1: bromodomain and PHD finger containing 1
- BTD: biotinidase

- C3orf14-Chromosome 3 open reading frame 14: predicted DNA binding protein.
- CFAP20DC: encoding protein Chromosome 3 open reading frame 67
- C3orf62: chromosome 3 open reading frame 62
- CACNA2D3: calcium channel, voltage-dependent, alpha 2/delta subunit 3
- CCR5: chemokine (C-C motif) receptor 5
- CGGBP1: CGG triplet repeat binding protein 1
- CMTM7: CKLF like MARVEL transmembrane domain containing 7
- CNTN4: Contactin 4
- COL7A1: Collagen, type VII, alpha 1 (epidermolysis bullosa, dystrophic, dominant and recessive)
- CRBN: Cereblon protein^[11]
- DCLK3: Doublecortin like kinase 3
- DLEC1: encoding protein Deleted in lung and esophageal cancer 1
- EAF1: ELL associated factor 1
- ENTPD3: ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 3
- FAM107A: Family with sequence similarity 107 member A
- FAM19A1: Family with sequence similarity 19 member A1, C-C motif chemokine like
- FBXL2: F-box and leucine rich repeat protein 2
- FOXP1: Forkhead Box Protein P1
- FRA3A encoding protein Fragile site, aphidicolin type, common, fra(3)(p24.2)
- FRMD4B encoding protein FERM domain containing 4B
- GHRLOS: non-coding RNA ghrelin opposite strand (non-protein coding)
- GMPPB: GDP-mannose pyrophosphorylase B
- HACL1: encoding protein 2-hydroxyacyl-CoA lyase 1
- HEMK1: encoding protein HemK methyltransferase family member 1
- HIGD1A: HIG1 domain family member 1A
- HTD2: encoding protein Hydroxyacyl-thioester dehydratase type 2
- LARS2: leucyl-tRNA synthetase, mitochondrial
- LIMD1: LIM domain-containing protein 1
- LOC105377021: encoding protein LOC105377021
- LINC00312: Long intergenic non-protein-coding RNA 312
- LZTFL1: Leucine zipper transcription factor like 1
- MIR138-1: encoding protein MicroRNA 138-1
- MIR885: encoding protein MicroRNA 885
- MITF: microphthalmia-associated transcription factor
- MLH1: mutL homolog 1, colon cancer, nonpolyposis type 2 (E. coli)
- MYRIP: Myosin VIIA and Rab interacting protein
- NBEAL2: Neurobeachin-like 2
- NDUFAF3: encoding enzyme NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] 1 alpha subcomplex assembly factor 3
- NKTR: NK-tumor recognition protein
- NPRL2: Nitrogen permease regulator 2-like protein
- OXTR: oxytocin receptor
- PCAF: acetyltransferase activity
- PHF7 encoding protein PHD finger protein 7
- PRICKLE2: encoding protein Prickle planar cell polarity protein 2

- PTHR1: parathyroid hormone receptor 1
- QRICH1: encoding protein QRICH1, also known as Glutamine-rich protein 1,
- RBM6: RNA-binding protein 6
- RPP14: Ribonuclease P protein subunit p14
- SCN5A: sodium channel, voltage-gated, type V, alpha (long QT syndrome 3)
- SETD5: SET domain containing 5
- SFMBT1: Scm-like with four mbt domains 1
- SLC25A20: solute carrier family 25 (carnitine/acylcarnitine translocase), member 20
- STT3B: catalytic subunit of the oligosaccharyltransferase complex
- SYNPR: synaptopodin
- TAFA4: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 19 member A4, C-C motif chemokine like
- TCAIM: encoding protein T-cell activation inhibitor, mitochondrial
- TDGF1: Teratocarcinoma-derived growth factor 1
- TMEM158: Transmembrane protein 158
- TMIE: transmembrane inner ear
- TRAK1: trafficking kinesin-binding protein 1
- TRANK1: encoding protein Tetratricopeptide repeat and ankyrin repeat containing 1
- TLL3: encoding protein Tubulin tyrosine ligase-like family, member 3
- TUSC2: tumor suppressor candidate 2
- UCN2: Urocortin-2
- ULK4: UNC-51 like kinase 4
- VGLL3: vestigial-like family member 3
- VHL: von Hippel-Lindau tumor suppressor
- ZMYND10: zinc finger MYND-type containing 10
- ZNF197: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 197
- ZNF502: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 502
- ZNF620: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 620
- ZNF621: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 621
- ZNF717: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 717

q-arm

Partial list of the genes located on q-arm (long arm) of human chromosome 3:

- ADIPOQ: adiponectin
- AMOTL2: encoding protein Angiomotin-like protein 2
- ARHGAP31: Rho GTPase activating protein 31
- BCHE: butyrylcholinesterase
- C3orf70 chromosome 3 open reading frame 70
- CAMPD1: Camptodactyly
- CCDC80: Coiled-coil domain containing protein 80
- CD200R1: Cell surface glycoprotein CD200 receptor 1
- CHST13: encoding protein Carbohydrate (chondroitin 4) sulfotransferase 13
- CLDND1: Claudin domain containing 1
- CPN2: Carboxypeptidase N subunit 2

- CPOX: coproporphyrinogen oxidase (coproporphyrin, harderoporphyrin)
- DPPA2: Developmental pluripotency associated 2
- DTX3L: encoding protein Deltex e3 ubiquitin ligase 3l
- DZIP3: encoding protein DAZ interacting zinc finger protein 3
- EAF2: ELL associated factor 2
- EFCC1: EF-hand and coiled-coil domain containing 1
- ETM1: Essential tremor 1
- ETV5: ETS variant 5
- FAM3D: family with sequence similarity 3, member D
- FAM43A: family with sequence similarity 43 member A
- FAM162A: family with sequence similarity 162 member A
- FBXO40: encoding protein F-box protein 40
- FILIP1L: encoding protein Filamin A interacting protein 1 like
- GYG1: Glycogenin-1
- HACD2 encoding protein 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2
- HGD: homogentisate 1,2-dioxygenase (homogentisate oxidase)
- IFT122: intraflagellar transport gene 122
- KIAA1257: KIAA1257
- LINC01279: encoding protein long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1279
- LNCR5: encoding protein lung cancer susceptibility 5
- LMLN: encoding protein Leishmanolysin-like (metallopeptidase M8 family)
- LRRC15: leucine rich repeat containing 15
- LSG1: large subunit GTPase 1 homolog
- MB21D2: encoding protein Mab-21 domain containing 2
- MCCC1: methylcrotonoyl-Coenzyme A carboxylase 1 (alpha)
- MORC1: encoding protein Morc family cw-type zinc finger 1
- MYLK: Telokin
- NEPRO: encoding protein Nucleolus and neural progenitor protein
- NFKBIZ: NF-kappa-B inhibitor zeta
- OTOL1: encoding glycoprotein Otolin
- PARP14 encoding protein Poly(ADP-ribose) polymerase family member 14
- PCCB: propionyl Coenzyme A carboxylase, beta polypeptide
- PDCD10: programmed cell death 10
- PIK3CA: phosphoinositide-3-kinase, catalytic, alpha polypeptide
- PISRT1: long non-coding RNA
- PROSER1: Proline and serine rich protein 1
- RAB7: RAB7, member RAS oncogene family
- RASA2: encoding protein Ras p21 protein activator 2
- RETNLB: resistin-like beta
- RHO: rhodopsin visual pigment
- RIOX2: Ribosomal oxygenase 2
- SELT: Selenoprotein T
- SEN7: Sentrin-specific protease 7
- SERP1: Stress-associated endoplasmic reticulum protein 1

- SOX2: transcription factor
- SOX2OT: SOX2 overlapping transcript
- SPG14 encoding protein Spastic paraplegia 14 (autosomal recessive)
- SRPRB: Signal recognition particle receptor subunit beta
- TEX55: encoding protein Testis expressed 55
- TIMMDC1: TIMMDC1
- TMEM44: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 44
- TM4SF1: Transmembrane 4 L6 family member 1
- TMPRSS7: encoding protein Transmembrane serine protease 7
- TP63: Tumor protein p63
- TRAT1: T-cell receptor-associated transmembrane adapter 1
- USH3A: Usher syndrome 3A
- ZBED2: encoding protein Zinc finger BED-type containing 2
- ZNF9: zinc finger protein 9 (a cellular retroviral nucleic acid binding protein)

Diseases and disorders

- 3-Methylcrotonyl-CoA carboxylase deficiency
- 3q29 microdeletion syndrome
- Acute myeloid leukemia (AML)
- Alkaptonuria
- Arrhythmogenic right ventricular dysplasia
- Atransferrinemia
- Autism
- Autosomal dominant optic atrophy
- ADOA plus syndrome
- Biotinidase deficiency
- Blepharophimosis, epicanthus inversus and ptosis type 1
- Breast/colon/lung/pancreatic cancer
- Brugada syndrome
- Castillo fever
- Carnitine-acylcarnitine translocase deficiency
- Cataracts
- Cerebral cavernous malformation
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease, type 2
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease
- Chromosome 3q duplication syndrome
- Coproporphyrinuria
- A location on human chromosome 3 is associated with respiratory failure and possibly with increased severity in COVID-19
- Dandy–Walker syndrome
- Deafness
- Diabetes
- Dystrophic epidermolysis bullosa
- Endplate acetylcholinesterase deficiency
- Essential tremors
- Ectrodactyly, Case 4
- Glaucoma, primary open angle
- Glycogen storage disease
- Hailey–Hailey disease
- Harderoporphyria
- Heart block, progressive/nonprogressive
- Hereditary coproporphyrinuria
- Hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer
- HIV infection, susceptibility/resistance to
- Hypobetalipoproteinemia, familial
- Hypothermia
- Leukoencephalopathy with vanishing white matter
- Long QT syndrome
- Lymphomas
- Malignant hyperthermia susceptibility
- Metaphyseal chondrodysplasia, Murk Jansen type
- Microcoria
- Möbius syndrome
- Moyamoya disease
- Mucopolysaccharidosis
- Muir–Torre family cancer syndrome

chromosome 4

Gene list

- AASDH: aminoadipate-semialdehyde dehydrogenase
- ACVR1: activin-like kinase 2 (ALK-2)
- ACOX3: encoding enzyme Peroxisomal acyl-coenzyme A oxidase 3
- AFAP1-AS1: encoding protein AFAP1 antisense RNA 1
- AGA: AGU syndrome (Finnish heritage disease) related gene

- AGPAT9: encoding enzyme Glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase 3 a.k.a. 1-acylglycerol-3-phosphate O-acyltransferase 9
- ANK2: ankyrin 2, neuronal
- APBB2: encoding protein Amyloid beta A4 precursor protein-binding family B member 2
- ART3: encoding enzyme Ecto-ADP-ribosyltransferase 3
- ASAH1: encoding enzyme N-acylethanolamine-hydrolyzing acid amidase
- BANK1: encoding protein B cell scaffold protein with ankyrin repeats 1
- BEND4: encoding protein BEN domain containing 4
- CCDC109B: Coiled-coil domain containing 109B
- CLNK: encoding protein Cytokine dependent hematopoietic cell linker
- Complement Factor I: Complement Factor I
- COL25A1-DT: encoding protein Zinc finger, cchc domain containing 23
- CRMP1: Collapsin response mediator protein 1, a member of CRMP family
- CSN2: Beta-casein
- CXCL1: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1, *scyb1*
- CXCL2: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 2, *scyb2*
- CXCL3: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 3, *scyb3*
- CXCL4: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 4, Platelet factor-4, PF-4, *scyb4*
- CXCL5: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 5, *scyb5*
- CXCL6: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 6, *scyb6*
- CXCL7: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 7, PPBP, *scyb7*
- CXCL8: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 8, interleukin 8 (IL-8), *scyb8*
- CXCL9: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 9, *scyb9*
- CXCL10: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 10, *scyb10*
- CXCL11: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 11, *scyb11*
- CXCL13: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 13, *scyb13*
- CYTL1: Cytokine-like 1
- DCUN1D4: Defective in cullin neddylation 1 domain containing 4
- DHX15: DEAH-box helicase 15
- DKK2: Dickkopf-related protein 2
- DMAC1: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 261
- DUX4: Thought to be inactive but 2010 research shows a key role in FSHD^[12]
- ELMOD2: Elmo domain-containing 2
- EMCN: Endomucin
- EVC: Ellis–Van Creveld syndrome
- EVC2: Ellis–Van Creveld syndrome 2 (limbin)
- Factor XI: Mutations cause Haemophilia C
- FAM114A1: Family with sequence similarity 114, member A1
- FAM149A: Family with sequence similarity 149, member A
- FAM193A: Family with sequence similarity 193, member A
- FAM198B: encoding protein Protein ENED
- FAM221B: Family with sequence similarity 221, member B
- FAM47E-STBD1: FAM47E-STBD1 readthrough

- FGF2: Fibroblast growth factor 2 (basic fibroblast growth factor)
- FGFR3: fibroblast growth factor receptor 3 (achondroplasia, thanatophoric dwarfism, bladder cancer)
- FGFRL1: fibroblast growth factor receptor-like 1
- FRG1: FSHD region gene 1
- FRYL: encoding protein FRY like transcription coactivator
- FSTL5: encoding protein Follistatin like 5
- GUF1: GUF1 homolog, GTPase
- HDL3: encoding Huntington-like neurodegenerative disorder 2 protein
- HELQ: encoding protein Helicase, POLQ-like
- HTT (Huntingtin): huntingtin protein (Huntington's disease)
- IGJ: linker protein for immunoglobulin alpha and mu polypeptides
- INTS12: Integrator complex subunit 12
- KDR: Kinase insert domain receptor (Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2)
- KIAA1530: UV stimulated scaffold protein A
- LCORL: Ligand dependent nuclear receptor corepressor like
- LDB2: LIM domain-binding protein 2
- LG2: Leucine-rich repeat LGI family member 2
- LOC100505912 encoding protein Uncharacterized LOC100505912
- LSM6: U6 snRNA-associated Sm-like protein
- LTO1P1: encoding protein Oral cancer overexpressed 1 pseudogene 1
- LYAR: Cell growth-regulating nucleolar protein
- MAB21L2: Mab-21-like 2
- Marcks1: encoding protein MARCKS-like 1
- MAML3: Mastermind-like 3
- MFSD7: encoding protein Major facilitator superfamily domain containing 7
- MIR1269A: microRNA 1269a
- MIR95: non-coding RNA MicroRNA 95
- MLF1IP: Centromere protein U
- MMAA: methylmalonic aciduria (cobalamin deficiency) cblA type
- MTHFD2L: NAD-dependent methylenetetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase 2-like protein
- MYL5: Myosin light chain 5
- NAP1L5: encoding protein Nucleosome assembly protein 1 like 5
- NDNF: encoding protein Neuron derived neurotrophic factor
- NOA1: encoding protein Nitric oxide associated 1
- NPNT: encoding protein Nephronectin
- NUDT6: nudix hydrolase 6
- NUDT9: nudix hydrolase 9
- OTUD4: OTU domain-containing protein 4
- PABPC4L: encoding protein Poly(A) binding protein, cytoplasmic 4-like
- PARM1: Prostate androgen-regulated mucin-like protein 1
- PHOX2B: codes for a homeodomain transcription factor
- P4K2B: Phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase type 2-beta
- PKD2: polycystic kidney disease 2 (autosomal dominant)
- PLAC8: encoding protein Placenta specific 8

- PLK4: Serine/threonine-protein kinase PLK4
- PPEF2: encoding protein Protein phosphatase with ef-hand domain 2
- PSAPL1: encoding protein Prosaposin-like 1 (gene/pseudogene)
- QDPR: quinoid dihydropteridine reductase
- RBM47: RNA binding motif protein 47
- RG9MTD2: encoding protein RNA (guanine-9-) methyltransferase domain containing 2
- SCRG1: encoding protein Stimulator of chondrogenesis 1
- SDAD1: protein SDA1 homolog
- SEC24B: Sec24 homolog B
- SEC24D: Sec24 homolog D
- SEPT11: Septin-11
- SLC9B2: solute carrier family 9 member B2
- SLC10A4: solute carrier family 10 member 4
- SMIM20: encoding protein Small integral membrane protein 20
- SNCA: synuclein, alpha (non A4 component of amyloid precursor)
- SPATA5: Spermatogenesis-associated protein 5
- STATH: gene with protein product
- TACC3: Transforming acidic coiled-coil-containing protein 3
- TENM3: Teneurin transmembrane protein 3
- THAP6: THAP domain-containing protein 6
- TMEM155: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 155
- TMEM165: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 165
- TMEM175: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 175
- TMEM243: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 243
- TMPRSS11D: Transmembrane protease, serine 11D
- TMPRSS11F: encoding protein Transmembrane serine protease 11F
- TNIP2: TNFAIP3-interaction protein 2
- TNIP3: encoding protein TNFAIP3 interacting protein 3
- UCHL1: ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal esterase L1 (ubiquitin thiolesterase)
- UGDH-AS1: encoding protein UGDH antisense RNA 1
- UGT8: UDP glycosyltransferase 8
- UNC5C: netrin receptor UNC5C
- UPF0602: encoding UPF0602 Protein C4orf47
- USP38: encoding protein Ubiquitin specific peptidase 38
- USP53: ubiquitin specific peptidase 53
- UTP3: small subunit processome component
- WFS1: Wolfram syndrome 1 (wolframin)
- ZGRF1: zinc-finger GRF-type containing 1
- ZNF621: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 621

Diseases and disorders

- Achondroplasia

- Autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease (PKD-2)
- Bladder cancer
- Crouzonodermoskeletal syndrome
- Chronic lymphocytic leukemia
- Congenital central hypoventilation syndrome
- Ellis–Van Creveld syndrome
- Facioscapulohumeral muscular dystrophy
- Fibrodysplasia ossificans progressiva (FOP)
- Haemophilia C
- Huntington's disease
- Hemolytic uremic syndrome
- Hereditary benign intraepithelial dyskeratosis
- Hirschprung's disease
- Hypochondroplasia
- Methylmalonic acidemia
- Mucopolysaccharidosis type I
- Muenke syndrome
- Nonsyndromic deafness
- Nonsyndromic deafness, autosomal dominant
- Parkinson's disease
- Polycystic kidney disease
- Romano–Ward syndrome
- SADDAN
- Tetrahydrobiopterin deficiency
- Thanatophoric dysplasia
 - Type 1
 - Type 2
- Wolfram syndrome
- Wolf–Hirschhorn syndrome

chromosomes 5

Gene list

- ABLIM3: encoding protein Actin-binding LIM protein 3
- ADAMTS2: ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif, 2
- AGXT2: Alanine-glyoxylate aminotransferase 2
- ANKRD31: encoding protein Ankyrin repeat domain 31
- APBB3: encoding protein Amyloid beta A4 precursor protein-binding family B member 3
- APC: adenomatosis polyposis coli

- ARL15: encoding protein ADP-ribosylation factor-like 15
- BRX1: Ribosome biogenesis protein BRX1 homolog (also BXDC2)
- C1QTNF3: Complement C1q tumor necrosis factor-related protein 3
- C5orf45: Chromosome 5 open reading frame 45
- C5orf47: encoding protein Chromosome 5 open reading frame 47
- C5orf49: encoding protein Chromosome 5 open reading frame 49
- CAST: Calpastatin
- CDO1: encoding protein Cysteine dioxygenase type 1
- CPLANE1: Ciliogenesis And Planar Polarity Effector 1
- CPLX2: Complexin-2
- CREBRF: encoding protein CREB3 regulatory factor
- CXXC5: CXXC-type zing finger protein 5
- DPYSL3: Dihydropyrimidinase-like protein 3
- EGR1: early growth response protein 1
- ERAP1: endoplasmic reticulum aminopeptidase 1 (previously called ARTS-1)
- ERAP2: endoplasmic reticulum aminopeptidase 2
- ESM1: Endothelial cell-specific molecule 1
- DTDST: diastrophic dysplasia sulfate transporter
- EIF4E1B: encoding protein Eukaryotic translation initiation factor 4E family member 1B
- ERCC8: excision repair cross-complementing rodent repair deficiency, complementation group 8
- FAF2: encoding protein Fas associated factor family member 2
- FAM172A: encoding protein UPF0528 protein FAM172A
- FAM105B: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 105, member B
- FAM114A2: encoding protein FAM114A2
- FAM71B: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 71 member B
- FASTKD3: FAST kinase domain-containing protein 3
- FBXL7: F-box/LRR-repeat protein 7
- FCHSD1: FCH and double SH3 domain protein 1
- FGF1: fibroblast growth factor 1 (acidic fibroblast growth factor)
- FGFR4: fibroblast growth factor receptor 4
- GM2A: GM2 ganglioside activator
- GNPDA1: Glucosamine-6-phosphate isomerase 1
- GPBP1: Vasculin
- HEXB: hexosaminidase B (beta polypeptide)
- HMGXB3: encoding protein HMG-box containing 3
- IK: Protein Red
- IRX1: Iroquois-class homeodomain protein (human)
- LARP1: La-related protein 1
- LMAN2: Lectin mannose binding 2
- LNCR3 encoding protein Lung cancer susceptibility 3
- LPCAT1: Lysophosphatidylcholine acyltransferase 1
- LYRM7: encoding protein LYR motif containing 7
- LYSMD3: LysM and putative peptidoglycan-binding domain-containing protein 3
- MAN2A1: Alpha-mannosidase 2

- MASS1: monogenic, audiogenic seizure susceptibility 1 homolog (mouse)
- MCC: Colorectal mutant cancer protein
- MCCC2: methylcrotonoyl-Coenzyme A carboxylase 2 (beta)
- MCEF: transcription factor AF4/FMR2 family, member 4
- MEF2C: Myocyte-specific enhancer factor 2C
- MEF2C-AS1: encoding protein MEF2C antisense RNA 1
- MGAT1: Mannosyl (alpha-1,3-)-glycoprotein beta-1,2-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase
- MINAR2: encoding protein Kiaa1024 like
- MIR1271: encoding MicroRNA 1271
- MIR146A: microRNA 146a
- MTRR: 5-methyltetrahydrofolate-homocysteine methyltransferase reductase
- MZB1: Marginal zone B and B1 cell-specific protein
- NIPBL: Nipped-B homolog (Drosophila)
- NREP: Neuronal regeneration related protein
- NSA2 encoding protein TGF beta-inducible nuclear protein 1
- NSD1: Transcription coregulator protein
- NSUN2: NOP2/Sun domain family, member 2
- NR2F1: Nuclear hormone receptor
- NSG2: encoding protein Hmp19 protein
- NUDCD2: NudC domain-containing protein 2
- P4HA2: Prolyl 4-hydroxylase subunit alpha-2
- PCBD2: Pterin-4-alpha-carbinolamine dehydratase 2
- PELO: Pelota homolog
- PGGT1B: encoding protein Protein geranylgeranyltransferase type I subunit beta
- PHAX: Phosphorylated adapter for RNA export
- Pikachurin: Responsible for the functioning of the ribbon synapses; allows the eye to track moving objects
- PFDN1: Prefoldin subunit 1
- POLR3G: encoding protein Polymerase (RNA) III (DNA directed) polypeptide G (32kD)
- PPIP5K2: Diphosphoinositol pentakisphosphate kinase 2
- PRCC1: Proline-rich coiled coil 1
- PRR16: encoding protein Proline-rich protein 16
- PURA: Purine-rich element-binding protein A
- PWWP2A: encoding protein PWWP domain containing 2A
- RANBP3L: encoding protein RAN binding protein 3-like
- RASGEF1C: encoding protein RasGEF domain family member 1C
- RMND5B: Required for meiotic nuclear division 5 homolog B
- SFXN1: Sideroflexin-1
- SKIV2L2: Ski2 like RNA helicase 2
- SLC22A5: solute carrier family 22 (organic cation transporter), member 5
- SLC26A2: solute carrier family 26 (sulfate transporter), member 2
- SH3TC2: domain and tetratricopeptide repeats 2
- SLCO4C1: Solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 4c1
- SLU7: pre-mRNA-splicing factor SLU7
- SMN1: survival motor neuron 1, telomeric

- SMN2: survival motor neuron 2, centromeric
- SNCAIP: synuclein, alpha interacting protein (synphilin)
- SPEF2: Sperm flagellar protein 2
- SPINK5: serine protease inhibitor Kazal-type 5 (LEKTI)
- SPINK6: serine protease inhibitor Kazal-type 6
- SPINK9: serine protease inhibitor Kazal-type 9 (LEKTI-2)
- SPZ1: Spermatogenic leucine zipper protein 1
- STC2: Stanniocalcin-2
- TBCA: Tubulin-specific chaperone A
- TCOF1: Treacher Collins-Franceschetti syndrome 1
- TGFB1: keratoepithelin
- THG1L: Probable tRNA(His) guanylyltransferase
- TICAM2: TIR domain-containing adapter molecule 2
- TMEM171: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 171
- TNFAIP8: Tumor necrosis factor, alpha-induced protein 8
- TSSK1B: encoding protein Testis specific serine kinase 1b
- TTC37: Tetratricopeptide repeat domain 37
- UPF0488: encodes G protein-coupled receptor protein signaling pathway
- YIPF5: Yip1 domain family member 5
- YTHDC2: encoding protein YTH domain containing 2
- ZBED3: Zinc finger BED domain-containing protein 3
- ZNF608: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 608

Diseases and disorders

- Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder
- Achondrogenesis type 1B
- Atelosteogenesis, type II
- Bipolar disorder
- Bosch-Boonstra-Schaaf optic atrophy syndrome
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease, type 4
- Cockayne syndrome
- Cornelia de Lange syndrome
- Corneal dystrophy of Bowman layer
- Cri du chat
- Diastrophic dysplasia
- Ehlers-Danlos syndrome
- Familial adenomatous polyposis
- Granular corneal dystrophy type I
- Granular corneal dystrophy type II
- GM2-gangliosidosis, AB variant
- Homocystinuria
- 3-Methylcrotonyl-CoA carboxylase deficiency
- Myelodysplastic syndrome
- Netherton syndrome
- Nicotine dependency
- Parkinson's disease
- Primary carnitine deficiency
- Recessive multiple epiphyseal dysplasia
- Sandhoff disease
- Spinal muscular atrophy
- Sotos Syndrome
- Survival motor neuron spinal muscular atrophy
- Treacher Collins syndrome
- Tricho-hepato-enteric syndrome
- Usher syndrome

Chromosomes 6

Gene list

p-arm

- ADTRP: encoding protein Androgen-dependent TFPI-regulating protein
- APOM: encoding protein Apolipoprotein M (6p21.33)
- ARMC12: encoding protein Armadillo repeat containing 12
- ATXN1: encoding protein Ataxin 1 (6p16.3-p16.76)
- TSBP1: encoding protein TSBP1 (6p21.32)
- C6orf62: chromosome 6 open reading frame 62 (6p22.3)
- C6orf89: chromosome 6 open reading frame 89 (6p21.2)
- CDKAL1: CDK5 regulatory subunit associated protein 1 like 1 (6p22.3)
- COL11A2: collagen, type XI, alpha 2(6p21.3)
- CRIP3: encoding protein Cysteine rich protein 3
- CYP21A2: cytochrome P450, family 21, subfamily A, polypeptide 2 (6p21.33)
- DHX16: DEAH-box helicase 16 (6p21.33)
- DOM3Z: Decapping exoribonuclease (6p21.33)
- DSP: Desmoplakin gene linked to cardiomyopathy (6p24.3)
- ELOVL5: ELOVL fatty acid elongase 5 (6p12.1)
- FBXO9: F-box protein 9 (6p12.1)
- FOXP4-AS1: encoding protein FOXP4 antisense RNA 1
- FTH1P5: encoding protein Ferritin, heavy polypeptide 1 pseudogene 5
- G6B: Protein G6b (6p21.33)
- GCNT2: N-acetyllactosaminide beta-1,6-N-acetylglucosaminyl-transferase (6p24.3)
- GGNBP1: encoding protein Gametogenetin binding protein 1 (pseudogene)
- GMD5: GDP-mannose 4,6-dehydratase (6p25.3)
- GTPBP2: encoding protein Gtp binding protein 2
- HCG4P11: HLA complex group 4 pseudogene 11
- HFE: hemochromatosis (6p22.2)
- HIST1H2AH: histone cluster 1 H2A family member h (6p22.1)
- HLA-A, HLA-B, HLA-C: major histocompatibility complex (MHC), class I, A, B, and C loci. (6p21.3)
- HLA-DQA1 and HLA-DQB1 form HLA-DQ heterodimer MHC class II, DQ: Celiac1, IDDM (6p21.3)

- HLA-DRA, HLA-DRB1, HLA-DRB3, HLA-DRB4, HLA-DRB5 forms HLA-DR, heterodimer MHC class II, DR (6p21.3) Mold / Biotxin Susceptibility
- HLA-DPA1 and HLA-DPB1 forms HLA-DP, MHC class II, DP (6p21.3)
- HLA-Cw*06:02: gene variation related to psoriasis (6p21.3)
- KAAG1: encoding protein Kidney associated antigen 1
- LOC100533655: encoding protein Aryl hydrocarbon receptor pseudogene
- LST1: leukocyte specific transcript 1 (6p21.33)
- LY6G6E encoding protein Lymphocyte antigen 6 complex, locus G6E (pseudogene) (6p21.33)
- MIR4640: microRNA 4640 (6p21.33)
- MLIP: muscular LMNA interaction protein (6p12.1)
- MRPS18B: mitochondrial ribosomal protein S18B (6p21.33)
- MUT: methylmalonyl Coenzyme A mutase (6p12.3)
- NHLRC1: NHL repeat containing E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 1 (6p22.3)
- NOL7: nucleolar protein 7 (6p23)
- NQO2: N-ribosyl dihydronicotinamide:quinone reductase 2 (6p25.2)
- NRSN1: neurensin 1 (6p22.3)
- NUDT3: nudix hydrolase 3 (6p21.31)
- PFDN6: prefoldin subunit 6 (6p21.32)
- PHACTR1: phosphatase and actin regulator 1 (6p24.1)
- PKHD1: polycystic kidney and hepatic disease 1 (autosomal recessive) (6p21.2-p12)
- PRICKLE4: prickle planar cell polarity protein 4 (6p21.1)
- PRSS16: protease, serine 16 (6p22.1)
- PSMB8-AS1: PSMB8 antisense RNA 1 (head to head) (6p21.32)
- RAB44: encoding protein Rab44, member ras oncogene family
- RIPOR2: RHO family interacting cell polarization regulator 2 (6p22.3)
- RPL10A: encoding protein 60S ribosomal protein L10a (6p21.31)
- SKIV2L: Ski2 like RNA helicase (6p21.33)
- SSR1: signal sequence receptor subunit 1 (6p24.3)
- TCF19: transcription factor 19 (6p21.33)
- TCP11: t-complex 11 (6p21.31)
- TJAP1: tight junction associated protein 1 (6p21.1)
- TP53COR1 encoding protein Tumor protein p53 pathway corepressor 1 (non-protein coding)
- TMEM151B: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 151B
- TNXB: tenascin XB (6p21.3)
- TRAM2: translocation associated membrane protein 2 (6p12.2)
- TRIM38: encoding protein Tripartite motif containing 38
- TTBK1: encoding protein Tau tubulin kinase 1
- UBR2: ubiquitin protein ligase E3 component n-recogin 2 (6p21.2)
- UNC5CL: encoding protein Unc-5 homolog C (C. elegans)-like
- USP8P1: encoding protein Ubiquitin specific peptidase 8 pseudogene 1
- VEGF: vascular endothelial growth factor A (angiogenic growth factor) (6p21.1)
- VPS52: GARP complex subunit
- VWA7: encoding protein Von willebrand factor a domain containing 7
- ZKSCAN4: encoding protein zinc finger with KRAB and SCAN domains 4

- ZNF76: zinc finger protein 76 (6p21.31)
- ZNF193: zinc finger protein 193 (6p22.1)
- ZNRD1: zinc ribbon domain containing 1 (6p22.1)

q-arm

The following are some of the genes located on q-arm (long arm) of human chromosome 6:

- AIM1: encoding protein Absent in melanoma 1 protein (6q21)
- AI1: encoding protein Androgen-induced protein 1 (6q24.2)
- AKIRIN2: akirin 2 (6q15)
- ARG1: arginase 1 (6q23.2)
- BCKDHB: branched-chain keto acid dehydrogenase E1, beta polypeptide (maple syrup urine disease) (6q14.1)
- BMIQ3: body mass index QTL 3
- TMEM242 encoding transmembrane protein TMEM242
- C6orf203: encoding protein Chromosome 6 open reading frame 203
- C6orf58: chromosome 6 open reading frame 58 (6q22.33)
- CFAP206: encoding protein Cilia And Flagella Associated Protein 206
- CMD1F: cardiomyopathy, dilated 1F
- CMD1K: cardiomyopathy, dilated 1K
- CNR1: cannabinoid 1 receptor (6q14-q15)^[13]
- DACT2: encoding protein Dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2
- DFNB38: deafness, autosomal recessive 38
- DYX4: dyslexia susceptibility 4
- ECT2L: encoding protein Epithelial cell transforming sequence 2 oncogene-like
- ESR1: Estrogen receptor 1 (6q25)
- EYA4: eyes absent homolog 4 (*Drosophila*)(6q23.2)
- FBXL4: F-box and leucine rich repeat protein 4 (6q16.1-q16.2)
- FEB5: febrile convulsions 5
- HACE1: HECT domain and Ankyrin repeat containing, E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 1 (6q21)
- HEBP2: heme binding protein 2 (6q24.1)
- IDDM8: insulin dependent diabetes mellitus 8
- IDDM15: insulin dependent diabetes mellitus 15
- IFNGR: interferon- γ receptor gene (6q23-q24)
- IGF2R: insulin-like growth factor 2 receptor (6q25.3)
- IMPG1: interphotoreceptor matrix proteoglycan 1 (6q14.1)
- KIAA0408
- LGSN: encoding protein lengsin
- LIN28B: lin-28 homolog B (6q16.3-q21)
- MAN1A1: mannosidase alpha class 1A member 1 (6q22.31)
- MB21D1: encoding protein Mab-21 domain containing 1
- MCDR1: macular dystrophy, retinal, 1
- MDN1: midasin AAA ATPase 1 (6q15)
- MOXD1: monooxygenase DBH like 1 (6q23.2)
- MTO1: mitochondrial tRNA translation optimization 1 (6q13)

- MRT18: mental retardation, non-syndromic, autosomal recessive
- MRT28: mental retardation, non-syndromic, autosomal recessive
- MTRF1L: mitochondrial translational release factor 1 like (6q25.2)
- MYO6: myosin VI (6q14.1)
- NHEG1: encoding protein Neuroblastoma highly expressed 1
- OA3: ocular albinism 3
- OPRM1: μ -opioid receptors (6q24-q25)
- OTSC7: otosclerosis 7
- PLG: plasminogen (6q26)
- PBCRA1
- PARK2: Parkinson disease (autosomal recessive, juvenile) 2, parkin (6q26)
- PCMT1: protein-L-isoaspartate (D-aspartate) O-methyltransferase (6q25.1)
- PERP: p53 apoptosis effector related to PMP-22 (6q23.3)
- PKIB: cAMP-dependent protein kinase inhibitor beta (6p22.31)
- PLAGL1: (6q24.2)
- QRSL1: encoding protein Glutaminyl-trna synthase (glutamine-hydrolyzing)-like 1
- RCD1: retinal cone dystrophy 1
- RFPL4B: Ret finger protein like 4B
- RP63: retinitis pigmentosa 63
- SASH1: SAM and SH3 domain containing 1 (6q24.3-q25.1)
- SCZD5: schizophrenia disorder 5
- SEN6: senescence (cellular)-related 6
- SENP6: SUMO1/sentrin specific peptidase 6 (6q14.1)
- SERAC1: serine active site containing 1 (6q25.3)
- SERINC1: serine incorporator 1 (6q22.31)
- SF3B5: splicing factor 3b subunit 5 (6q24.2)
- SMAP1: small ArfGAP 1 (6q13)
- SOBP: sine oculis binding protein homolog (6q21)
- SPG25: spastic paraplegia 25
- ST8: suppression of tumorigenicity 8
- SYNJ2: synaptojanin 2 (6q25.3)
- T: T brachyury transcription factor (more commonly known as the T gene) linked to Hepatocellular carcinoma and Chordoma (6q27)^[14]
- TAAR1: trace amine associated receptor 1 (6q23.1)
- TAAR2: trace amine associated receptor 2 (6q24)
- TMEM200A: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 200A
- TSPYL1: TSPY like 1 (6q22.1)
- UNC93A: encoding protein Unc-93 homolog A (C. elegans)
- VNN1: vanin 1 (6q23.2)
- VNN2: vanin 2 (6q23.2)
- VTA1: Vesicle trafficking 1 (6q24.1-2)
- ZC2HC1: encoding protein Zinc finger C2HC-type containing 1B
- ZDHHC14: encoding protein Zinc finger, DHHC-type containing 14

Diseases and disorders

- ankylosing spondylitis, HLA-B
- collagenopathy, types II and XI
- Coeliac disease HLA-DQA1 & DQB1
- Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, classical, hypermobility, and Tenascin-X types
- Hashimoto's thyroiditis
- hemochromatosis
- Hemochromatosis type 1
- 21-hydroxylase deficiency
- maple syrup urine disease
- methylmalonic acidemia
- Autosomal nonsyndromic deafness
- North Carolina macular dystrophy
- otospondylomegalepiphyseal dysplasia
- Parkinson disease
- polycystic kidney disease
- porphyria
- porphyria cutanea tarda
- Rheumatoid arthritis, HLA-DR
- CIRS (Chronic Inflammatory Response Syndrome), Sick Building Syndrome, Mold Toxin Susceptibility / Poisoning, HLA-DR/DQ
- Spinocerebellar ataxia type 1, ATXN1
- Stickler syndrome, COL11A2
- Systemic lupus erythematosus
- Diabetes mellitus type 1, HLA-DR, DQA1 & DQB1
- X-linked sideroblastic anemia
- Epilepsy
- Guillain Barre Syndrome
- Chordoma
- Hepatocellular carcinoma
- Schizophrenia

chromosomes 7

Gene list

- AASS: encoding enzyme Alpha-aminoadipic semialdehyde synthase, mitochondrial
- ACTR3B: actin-related protein 3B
- AEBP1: AE binding protein 1
- AGK: encoding enzyme mitochondrial acylglycerol kinase
- ARHGEF35: encoding protein Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor (GEF) 35
- AVL9: encoding protein Avl9 cell migration associated
- BCAP29: B-cell receptor-associated protein 29
- BCC6: encoding protein basal cell carcinoma, susceptibility to, 6
- BRAT1: BRCA1-associated ATM activator 1
- C7orf25: protein UPF0415
- C7orf31: chromosome 7 open reading frame 31

- CALU: Calumenin
- CCL24: encoding protein C-C motif chemokine ligand 24
- CDCA7L: Cell division cycle-associated 7-like protein
- CFTR: anion channel membrane protein
- CNOT4: CCR4-NOT transcription complex, subunit 4
- CPED1: cadherin like and PC-esterase domain containing 1
- CPVL: carboxypeptidase, vitellogenic like
- CROT: Peroxisomal carnitine O-octanoyltransferase
- DDX56: DEAD-box helicase 56
- DMTF1: Cyclin D binding myb like transcription factor 1
- ECOP: EGFR-coamplified and overexpressed protein
- EEP1: encoding protein Endonuclease/exonuclease/phosphatase family domain containing 1
- EGFR-AS1: encoding protein EGFR antisense RNA 1
- EZH2: encoding enzyme histone-lysine N-methyltransferase for histone h3 lysine 27
- FAM71F2: family with sequence similarity 71 member F2
- FAM185A: family with sequence similarity 185 member A
- FAM200A: family with sequence similarity 200 member A
- FBXO24: F-box only protein 24
- GBAS: Glioblastoma amplified sequence; Protein NipSnap homolog 2
- GET4: encoding protein GET4
- GLCCI1: Glucocorticoid-induced transcript 1 protein
- HOXA@: encoding protein Homeobox a cluster
- HOXA10-HOXA9: readthrough gene unlikely to produce a protein product
- HPC4: Prostate cancer, hereditary, 4
- ICA1: islet cell autoantigen 1
- ING3: inhibitor of growth protein 3
- INTS1: encoding protein Integrator complex subunit 1
- IQCE: IQ domain-containing protein E
- KDM7A: encoding protein Lysine demethylase 7A
- LCHN: protein encoded by the KIAA1147 gene
- LHFPL3: LHFPL tetraspan subfamily member 3
- LINC01003: encoding long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1003
- LRRC17: leucine-rich repeat containing protein 17
- LRRC61: encoding protein Leucine rich repeat containing 61
- LRRD1: encoding protein Leucine-rich repeats and death domain containing 1
- LSM5: U6 small nuclear RNA and mRNA degradation associated
- LUC7L2: putative RNA-binding protein Luc7-like 2
- MACC1: encoding protein Macc1, met transcriptional regulator
- MAP11: encoding protein Microtubule-associated protein 11
- MDFIC: MyoD family inhibitor domain containing
- METTL2B: methyltransferase-like protein 2B
- MINDY4: MINDY lysine 48 deubiquitinase 4
- MIR93: encoding protein MicroRNA 93
- MIR148A: encoding protein MicroRNA 148a

- MIR196B: encoding protein MicroRNA 196b
- MIR548F4: encoding protein MicroRNA 548f-4
- MIR96: microRNA 96
- MOSPD3: motile sperm domain containing 3
- MTERF: mitochondrial transcription termination factor 1
- MTRNR2L6: encoding protein MT-RNR2-like 6
- NOM1: nucleolar protein with MIF4G domain 1
- NUDCD3: NudC domain-containing protein 3
- NUPL2: nucleoporin-like 2
- NXPH1: neurexophilin-1
- OPN1SW: blue-sensitive opsin
- PDAP1: PDGFA associated protein 1
- PHTF2: putative homeodomain transcription factor 2
- PLOD3: procollagen-lysine,2-oxoglutarate 5-dioxygenase 3
- POM121: POM121 transmembrane nucleoporin
- POP7: ribonuclease P protein subunit p20
- PPP1R17: protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 17
- PSPH: phosphoserine phosphatase
- PURB: purine-rich element binding protein B
- PVRIG: encoding protein Poliovirus receptor related immunoglobulin domain containing
- RADIL: ras-associating and dilute domain-containing protein
- RASA4B: encoding protein RAS p21 protein activator 4B
- RCP9: DNA-directed RNA polymerase III subunit RCP9
- REPIN1: replication initiator 1
- RNF216-IT1: encoding protein RNF216 intronic transcript 1
- SCIN: scinderin
- SCRN1: secernin 1
- SEMA3E: encoding protein Semaphorin 3E
- SOSTDC1: sclerostin domain containing 1
- SPDYE1: speedy/RINGO cell cycle regulator family member E1
- SSC4D: scavenger receptor cysteine rich family member with 4 domains
- STEAP1: six transmembrane epithelial antigen of the prostate 1
- STEAP2: six transmembrane epithelial antigen of the prostate 2
- STEAP4: six transmembrane epithelial antigen of the prostate 4
- STYXL1: serine/threonine/tyrosine-interacting-like protein 1
- SUMF2: sulatase-modifying factor 2
- SYPL1: synaptophysin-like protein 1
- TARP: TCR gamma alternate reading frame protein
- TBRG4: transforming growth factor beta regulator 4
- TECPR1 encoding protein Tectonin beta-propeller repeat containing 1
- TMED4: transmembrane emp24 domain-containing protein 4
- TMEM130: transmembrane protein 130
- TMEM196 encoding protein Transmembrane protein 196
- TMEM243: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 243

- TNRC18: encoding protein Trinucleotide repeat containing 18
- TRBC1 encoding protein T cell receptor beta constant 1
- TRBC2 encoding protein T cell receptor beta constant 2
- TRGV1: encoding protein T cell receptor gamma variable 1 (non-functional)
- TRIL: TRL4 interactor with leucine rich repeats
- UPK3B: encoding protein Uroplakin 3B
- URG4: up-regulated gene 4
- WBSCR17: polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 17
- WDR91 encoding protein WD repeat domain 91
- WEE2-AS1: encoding protein WEE2 antisense RNA 1
- XKR5: encoding protein XK, Kell blood group complex subunit-related family, member 5
- ZC3HAV1: zinc finger CCCH-type containing
- ZC3HC1: zinc finger C3HC-type containing 1
- ZNF106: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 106
- ZNF117: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 117
- ZNF394: zinc finger protein 394
- ZNF398: zinc finger protein 398
- ZNF679: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 679
- ZNF716: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 716
- ZNF727: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 727
- ZNF786: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 786
- ZNF853: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 853
- ZKSCAN1: zinc finger protein with KRAB and SCAN domains 1
- ZKSCAN5: zinc finger protein with KRAB and SCAN domains 5
- ZMIZ2: zinc finger MIZ domain-containing protein 2
- ZNF277P: zinc finger protein 277
- ZRF1: DnaJ heat shock protein family (Hsp40) member C2
- ZSCAN21: zinc finger and SCAN domain-containing protein 21

Diseases and disorders

- 7p22.1 microduplication syndrome
- argininosuccinic aciduria
- cerebral cavernous malformation
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease
- Cholestasis, progressive familial intrahepatic 3
- Citrullinemia, type II, adult-onset
- congenital bilateral absence of vas deferens
- cystic fibrosis
- Developmental verbal dyspraxia
- distal spinal muscular atrophy, type V
- Ehlers–Danlos syndrome
- hemochromatosis, type 3
- Hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer HNPCC4
- Lissencephaly syndrome, norman-roberts type
- Marfan syndrome
- maple syrup urine disease
- maturity onset diabetes of the young type 3
- mucopolysaccharidosis type VII or Sly syndrome
- Muscular dystrophy, limb-girdle, type 1D
- myelodysplastic syndrome
- Myotonia congenita

- nonsyndromic deafness
- osteogenesis imperfecta
- p47-phox-deficient chronic granulomatous disease
- Pectus excavatum
- Pendred syndrome
- Romano–Ward syndrome
- Shwachman–Diamond syndrome
- Schizophrenia
- Silver-Russell syndrome
- Specific language impairment
- Tritanopia or tritanomaly color blindness
- Williams syndrome
- Zellweger syndrome

chromosomes 8

Gene list

- ADHFE1 encoding protein Alcohol dehydrogenase, iron containing 1
- AEG1 : Astrocyte Elevated Gene (linked to hepatocellular carcinoma and neuroblastoma)
- ANK1: ankyrin 1, erythrocytic
- Arc/Arg3.1
- ASAH1: N-acylsphingosine amidohydrolase (acid ceramidase) 1
- ASPH: encoding enzyme Aspartyl/asparaginyl beta-hydroxylase
- AZIN1: encoding protein Antizyme inhibitor 1

- BRF2: transcription factor IIIB 50 kDa subunit
- C8orf32/WDYHV1: encoding enzyme Protein N-terminal glutamine amidohydrolase
- C8orf33: chromosome 8, open reading frame 33
- C8orf34: chromosome 8, open reading frame 34
- C8orf4: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein C8orf4
- C8orf48 encoding protein C8orf48
- C8orf58: chromosome 8 open reading frame 58
- C8orfk29: encoding protein TMEM249
- CCAT1: colon cancer associated transcript 1
- CCDC166: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 166
- CCDC25: coiled-coil domain containing protein 25
- CHD7: chromodomain helicase DNA binding protein 7
- CHMP4C: Charged multivesicular body protein 4c
- CHRAC1 encoding protein Chromatin accessibility complex 1
- CHRNA2: cholinergic receptor, nicotinic, alpha 2 (neuronal)
- CLN8: ceroid-lipofuscinosis, neuronal 8
- CNGB3: cyclic nucleotide gated channel beta 3
- COH1: vacuolar protein sorting 13B
- CRISPLD1 encoding protein Cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1
- CSGALNACT1: Chondroitin sulfate N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 1
- CTHRC1 encoding protein Collagen triple helix repeat containing 1
- CYP11B1: cytochrome P450, family 11, subfamily B, polypeptide 1
- CYP11B2: cytochrome P450, family 11, subfamily B, polypeptide 2
- DCSTAMP: dendrocyte expressed seven transmembrane protein
- DPYS: dihydropyrimidinase
- EBAG9: Estrogen receptor binding site associated antigen 9
- ENTPD4: encoding protein Ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 4
- EPPK1: epiplakin
- ERICH5 encoding protein Glutamate rich 5
- ESCO2: establishment of sister chromatid cohesion N-acetyltransferase 2
- EXT1: exostosin glycosyltransferase 1
- EXTL3: exostosin-like glycosyltransferase 3
- EYA1: EYA transcriptional coactivator and phosphatase 1
- FABP9: fatty acid binding protein 9, testis
- FAM167A: family with sequence similarity 167, member A
- FAM203B: family with sequence similarity 203, member B
- FAM83A: family with sequence similarity 83, member A
- FAM83H: family with sequence similarity 83, member H
- FAM84B: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 84 member b
- FBXO16 encoding protein F-box protein 16
- FDFT1 encoding protein Farnesyl-diphosphate farnesyltransferase 1
- FGFR1: fibroblast growth factor receptor 1 (fms-related tyrosine kinase 2, Pfeiffer syndrome)
- FGL1: Fibrinogen-like protein 1
- GDAP1: ganglioside-induced differentiation-associated protein 1

- GDF6: growth differentiation factor 6
- GPIHBP1: GPI-anchored high density lipoprotein binding protein 1
- GRINA: encoding protein Glutamate receptor, ionotropic, N-methyl D-aspartate-associated protein 1 (glutamate binding)
- GSDMC encoding protein Gasdermin C
- GULOP pseudogene: responsible for human inability to produce Vitamin C
- HGSNAT: heparan-alpha-glucosaminide N-acetyltransferase
- HMBOX1: encoding protein Homeobox containing 1, also known as homeobox telomere-binding protein 1 (HOT1)
- HRSP12 encoding enzyme Ribonuclease UK114
- INTS8: integrator complex subunit 8
- INTS9: integrator complex subunit 9
- KCNQ3: potassium channel, voltage gated KQT-like subfamily Q, member 3.
- KIAA0196: KIAA0196
- KIF13B encoding protein Kinesin family member 13B
- LACTB2: lactamase, beta 2
- LAPTM4B: lysosomal-associated transmembrane protein 4B
- LOC642658: encoding protein Basic helix-loop-helix transcription factor scleraxis
- LPL: lipoprotein lipase
- LSM1: U6 snRNA-associated Sm-like protein LSm1
- MAK16: MAK16 homolog
- MCPH1: microcephaly, primary autosomal recessive 1
- MIR486-1: encoding MicroRNA 486-1
- MIR548V: encoding MicroRNA 548v
- MIR5680: encoding MicroRNA 5680
- MIR6850 encoding protein MicroRNA 6850
- MRPL13 encoding protein Mitochondrial ribosomal protein L13
- MYBL1 encoding protein MYB proto-oncogene like 1
- NBN: nibrin
- NDRG1: N-myc downstream regulated gene 1
- NEF3: neurofilament 3 (150kDa medium)
- NEFL: neurofilament, light polypeptide 68kDa
- ODF1: outer dense fiber protein 1
- OTUD6B: OTU domain containing 6B
- PDP1: pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase catalytic subunit 1
- PKIA: cAMP-dependent protein kinase inhibitor alpha
- PLEC: plectin
- PNMA2: paraneoplastic antigen Ma2
- PREX2: phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate dependent Rac exchange factor 2
- PROSC: proline synthetase co-transcribe bacterial homolog protein
- PURG encoding protein Purine-rich element binding protein G
- PVT1: Pvt1 oncogene
- RECQL4: RecQ protein-like 4
- RNF5P1: ring finger protein 5 pseudogene 1

- RRS1: ribosome biogenesis regulator homolog
- RUNX1T1: runt-related transcription factor 1; translocated to, 1 (cyclin D-related)
- SFTPC: surfactant protein C
- SLC20A2: Sodium-dependent phosphate transporter 2
- SLURP1: secreted LY6/PLAUR domain containing 1
- SNAI2: snail homolog 2 (Drosophila)
- SPAG11B: sperm-associated antigen 11B
- STAU2: stauflen double-stranded RNA binding protein 2
- SYBU: Syntabulin
- TG: thyroglobulin
- THAP1: THAP domain containing, apoptosis associated protein 1
- TMEM67: encoding protein Meckelin
- TNFRSF11B: tumor necrosis factor receptor superfamily, member 11b
- TONSL: encoding protein Tonsoku-like, DNA repair protein
- TPA: tissue plasminogen activator
- TRMT12: tRNA methyltransferase 12 homolog
- TRPS1: trichorhinophalangeal syndrome I
- TSPYL5 (gene): encoding protein TSPY like 5
- TTI2 encoding protein TELO2 interacting protein 2
- VCP1P1: valosin containing protein/p47 complex interacting protein 1
- VXN: encoding vexin
- VMAT1: vesicular monoamine transporter protein
- VPS13B: vacuolar protein sorting 13 homolog B (yeast)
- VPS37A: vacuolar protein sorting 37 homolog A
- WRN: Werner syndrome
- YTHDF3: YTH N6-methyladenosine RNA binding protein 3
- ZFP41: encoding protein ZFP41 zinc finger protein
- ZHX2: zinc fingers and homeoboxes protein 2
- ZMAT4: zinc finger matrin-type 4
- ZNF16: zinc finger protein 16
- ZNF395: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 395
- ZNF517 encoding protein Zinc finger protein 517
- ZNF696 encoding protein Zinc finger protein 696
- ZNF703: zinc finger protein 703
- ZNF706: zinc finger protein 706
- ZNF707: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 707

Diseases and disorders

- 8p23.1 duplication syndrome
- Bipolar disorder
- Burkitt lymphoma
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease
- COACH syndrome
- Cleft lip and cleft palate
- Cohen syndrome
- Congenital hypothyroidism

- Fahr's syndrome
- Hereditary multiple exostoses
- Lipoprotein lipase deficiency, familial
- Myelodysplastic syndrome
- Pfeiffer syndrome
- Primary microcephaly
- Rothmund–Thomson syndrome
- Schizophrenia, associated with 8p21-22 locus
- Waardenburg syndrome
- Werner syndrome
- Pingelapese blindness
- Langer–Giedion syndrome
- Roberts syndrome
- Hepatocellular carcinoma
- Sanfilippo syndrome

chromosomes 9

1
2
3
4

Gene list

- ABO: ABO histo-blood group glycosyltransferases
- ACTL7A: encoding protein Actin-like protein 7A
- ADAMTS13: ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif, 13
- AIF1L: allograft inflammatory factor 1-like
- ALAD: aminolevulinate, delta-, dehydratase
- ALS4: amyotrophic lateral sclerosis 4
- ANGPTL2: angiopoietin-related protein 2
- ASS: argininosuccinate synthetase
- BANCR: encoding protein BRAF-activated non-protein coding RNA
- BNC2: zinc finger protein basonuclin-2
- C9orf64: chromosome 9 open reading frame 64

- C9orf78: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein C9orf78
- SHOC1: Shortage In Chiasmata 1
- C9orf25: encoding protein Chromosome 9 open reading frame 25
- C9orf43: encoding protein Chromosome 9 open reading frame 43
- C9orf135: encoding protein Chromosome 9 open reading frame 135
- C9orf152: chromosome 9 open reading frame 152
- C9orf156: encoding protein Chromosome 9 open reading frame 156
- CAAP1: caspase activity and apoptosis inhibitor 1
- CARD19: caspase recruitment domain family member 19
- CBWD1: COBW domain-containing protein 1
- CCDC180: Coiled coil domain-containing protein 180
- CCL21: chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 21, SCYA21
- CCL27: chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 27, SCYA27
- CFAP157: Cilia and flagella associated protein 157
- CHMP5: Charged multivesicular body protein 5
- CNTLN: centlein
- CDKN2BAS: CDKN2B antisense RNA 1 or antisense non-coding RNA in the INK4 locus (ANRIL)
- COL5A1: collagen, type V, alpha 1
- DDX31: DEAD box polypeptide 31
- DENND1A: DENN domain-containing protein 1A
- ENG: endoglin (Osler-Rendu-Weber syndrome 1)
- ENTPD2: encoding enzyme ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 2
- EQTN: equatorin
- FAM73B: family with sequence similarity 73 member B
- FAM120A: Family with sequence similarity 120 member A
- FAM122a: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 122A
- FBP1 Fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase 1
- FIBCD1: encoding protein Fibrinogen C domain containing 1
- FOCAD: focadhesin
- FXN: frataxin
- GALT: galactose-1-phosphate uridylyltransferase
- GAS1: growth arrest-specific protein 1
- GCNT1: glucosaminyl (N-acetyl) transferase 1
- GLE1L: Nucleoporin GLE1
- GPR107: G protein-coupled receptor 107
- GRHPR: glyoxylate reductase/hydroxypyruvate reductase
- GSN: cytoplasmic and plasma gelsolin
- HAUS6: HAUS augmin-like complex subunit 6
- HEMGN: encoding protein hemogen
- IFN1@: Interferon, type 1, cluster
- IKBKAP: inhibitor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells, kinase complex-associated protein
- INSL6: insulin like 6
- ISCA1: iron-sulfur cluster assembly 1 homolog, mitochondrial
- KIAA1958: protein KIAA1958

- KYAT1: Kynurenine aminotransferase 1
- LINGO2: leucine rich repeat and Ig domain containing 2
- LOC101928193: encoding protein LOC101928193
- MGC50722: Protein MGC50722, Uncharacterized Protein LOC399693
- MIR181A2HG encoding protein MIR181A2 host gene
- MIR7-1: microRNA 7-1
- MSMP: encoding protein Microseminoprotein, prostate associated
- MTAP: S-methyl-5'-thioadenosine phosphorylase
- NAA35: encoding protein N(alpha)-acetyltransferase 35, NatC auxiliary subunit
- NANS: N-acetylneuraminase synthase
- NINJ1: ninjurin-1
- NOL6: nucleolar protein 6
- NUDT2: nudix hydrolase 2
- OBP2B: encoding protein Odorant-binding protein 2B
- OLFM1: olfactomedin 1
- PHF2: PHD finger protein 2
- PHPT1: phosphohistidine phosphatase 1
- PIP5K1B: phosphatidylinositol-4-phosphate 5-kinase type-1 beta
- PLAA: phospholipase A-2-activating protein
- PMPCA: mitochondrial processing alpha subunit
- PRUNE2: protein prune homolog 2
- PTCH1: protein patched 1 transmembrane receptor protein
- RABGAP1: RAB GTPase activating protein 1
- REXO4: RNA exonuclease 4
- RNF183: encoding protein Ring finger protein 183
- SARDH: sarcosine dehydrogenase, mitochondrial
- SIT1: signaling threshold regulating transmembrane adapter 1
- SLC25A25-AS1: encoding protein SLC25A25 antisense RNA 1
- SNORD24: encoding protein small nucleolar RNA, C/D box 24
- SPAG8 sperm-associated antigen 8
- SPIN1: spindlin-1
- ST6GALNAC4 encoding enzyme ST6 (alpha-N-acetyl-neuraminyl-2,3-beta-galactosyl-1,3)-N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 4, also known as sialyltransferase 3C (SIAT3-C) or sialyltransferase 7D (SIAT7-D)
- ST6GALNAC6: ST6 N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 6
- STOML2: stomatin-like protein 2
- STRBP: spermatid perinuclear RNA-binding protein
- TEX10: testis expressed 10
- TGFBR1: transforming growth factor beta, receptor type I
- TMC1: transmembrane channel-like 1
- TMEM215: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 215
- TMEM268: Transmembrane protein 268
- TOR2A encoding protein Torsin-2A
- TSC1: tuberous sclerosis complex 1

- TTC39B: tetratricopeptide repeat protein 39B
- UBAC1: ubiquitin-associated domain containing protein 1
- UBAP1: ubiquitin-associated protein 1
- UBAP2: ubiquitin-associated protein 2
- ZBTB43: zinc finger and BTB domain containing 43
- ZCCHC6: zinc finger, CCHC domain containing 6
- ZDHHC21: zinc finger DHHC-type containing 21
- ZNF79: zinc finger protein 79
- ZNF367: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 367
- ZNF510: zinc finger protein 510

Diseases and disorders

- acytosiosis
- ALA-D deficiency porphyria
- Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
- citrullinemia
- Coronary artery disease
- chronic myelogenous leukemia (t9;22 - the Philadelphia chromosome)
- Diaphyseal Medullary Stenosis with Malignant Fibrous Histiosytoma (DMS-MFH, Hardcastle syndrome)
- Ehlers-Danlos syndrome
- familial dysautonomia
- Friedreich ataxia
- Frontotemporal_dementia
- galactosemia
- Gorlin syndrome or nevoid basal cell carcinoma syndrome
- hereditary hemorrhagic telangiectasia
- lethal congenital contracture syndrome
- nail-patella syndrome (NPS)
- nonsyndromic deafness
- OCD
- polycythemia vera
- porphyria
- primary hyperoxaluria
- Tangier disease
- tetrasomy 9p
- thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura
- trisomy 9
- tuberous sclerosis
- VLDLR-associated cerebellar hypoplasia

chromosomes 10

Gene list

- AFAP1L2: actin filament associated protein 1 like 2
- ALL1 encoding protein Leukemia, acute lymphocytic, susceptibility to, 1
- ALOX5: Arachidonate 5-Lipoxygenase (processes essential fatty acids to leukotrienes, which are important agents in the inflammatory response; also facilitates development and maintenance of cancer stem cells, slow-dividing cells thought to give rise to a variety of cancers, including leukemia)
- ANKRD22: encoding protein Ankyrin repeat domain 22
- ARHGAP21: rho GTPase activating protein 21
- ARID5B: encoding protein AT-rich interactive domain-containing protein 5B
- ARMH3: Armadillo Like Helical Domain Containing 3
- AS3MT: encoding enzyme Arsenite methyltransferase

- AVP11: encoding protein Arginine vasopressin-induced protein 1
- C10orf67: chromosome 10 open reading frame 67
- CAMK1D: calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase ID
- CCAR1: Cell division cycle and apoptosis regulator 1
- CCDC3: Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 3
- CCDC186: encoding protein CCDC186
- CCNY: Cyclin-Y
- CDC123: Cell division cycle protein 123 homolog
- CDH23: cadherin-like 23
- CDH23-AS1: CDH23 antisense RNA 1
- CDNF: cerebral dopamine neurotrophic factor
- CEFIP: encoding protein Cardiac-enriched FHL2-interacting protein
- COMMD3-BMI1: COMMD3-BMI1 readthrough
- CPXM2: encoding protein Carboxypeptidase x, m14 family member 2
- CUTC: Copper homeostasis protein cutC homolog
- CXCL12: chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 12, SDF-1, *scyb12*
- DDX50: DExD-box helicase 50
- DEPP: decidual protein induced by progesterone
- DHX32: DEAH-box helicase 32
- DIP2C: encoding protein Disco interacting protein 2 homolog c
- DKK1: Dickkopf-related protein 1
- DNAJC12: DnaJ (Hsp40) homolog, subfamily c, member 12
- DNAJC9: DnaJ (Hsp40) homolog, subfamily c, member 9
- DPYSL4: Dihydropyrimidinase-related protein 4
- EBLN1: encoding protein Endogenous Bornavirus-like nucleoprotein 1
- ECD: ecdysoneless cell cycle regulator
- EGR2: early growth response 2 (Krox-20 homolog, Drosophila)
- EIF5AP1: eukaryotic translation initiation factor 5A-like 1
- EPC1: Enhancer of polycomb homolog 1
- ERCC6: excision repair cross-complementing rodent repair deficiency, complementation group 6
- FAM107B: family with sequence similarity 107, member B
- FAM13C: family with sequence similarity 13, member C
- FAM170B: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 170 member B
- FAM188A: family with sequence similarity 188, member A
- FAM208b: encoding protein FAM208b
- FAM213A: family with sequence similarity 213, member A
- FAM25BP encoding protein Protein FAM25
- FAS-AS1, long non-coding RNA
- FBXL15: encoding protein F-box and leucine rich repeat protein 15
- FGFR2: fibroblast growth factor receptor 2 (bacteria-expressed kinase, keratinocyte growth factor receptor, craniofacial dysostosis 1, Crouzon syndrome, Pfeiffer syndrome, Jackson–Weiss syndrome)
- FRA10AC1: Fragile site, folic acid type
- FRAT1: WNT signaling pathway regulator
- FRAT2: WNT signaling pathway regulator

- FRMPD2 encoding protein FERM and PDZ domain containing 2
- GATA3: encoding the GATA3 transcription factor. GATA3 is critical for the embryonic development of the parathyroid gland, neural component of hearing, and kidney. Haploinsufficiency of the gene underlies a rare disorder, the hypoparathyroidism, deafness, and renal dysplasia syndrome
- GHITM: growth hormone-inducible transmembrane protein
- GPR15LG: encoding protein GPR15LG, GPR15 ligand
- GPRIN2: G protein-regulated inducer of neurite outgrowth 2
- GTPBP4: Nucleolar GTP-binding protein 4
- HELLS: Lymphoid-specific helicase
- HKDC1: hexokinase domain containing 1
- KIN: DNA/RNA-binding protein KIN17
- LHPP: encoding protein Phospholysine phosphohistidine inorganic pyrophosphate phosphatase
- MTG1: mitochondrial GTPase 1
- NPM3: nucleoplasmin-3
- NRBF2: nuclear receptor-binding factor 2
- NSMCE4A: non-SMC element 4 homolog A
- OTUD1: encoding protein OTU deubiquitinase 1
- PAPSS2: encoding enzyme bifunctional 3'-phosphoadenosine 5'-phosphosulfate synthase 2
- PCBD1: 6-pyruvoyl-tetrahydropterin synthase/dimerization cofactor of hepatocyte nuclear factor 1 alpha (TCF1)
- PCDH15: protocadherin 15
- PI4K2A: phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase 2-alpha
- PIP4K2A: phosphatidylinositol 5 phosphate 4-kinase type-2 alpha
- PITRM1: pitrilysin metallopeptidase 1
- PLEKHS1 encoding protein Pleckstrin homology domain containing S1
- PLXDC2: plexin domain-containing protein 2
- PRAP1: encoding protein Proline rich acidic protein 1
- PROSER2: proline and serine rich 2 or c10orf47
- PTEN gene: phosphatase and tensin homolog (mutated in multiple advanced cancers 1)
- RET: ret proto-oncogene (multiple endocrine neoplasia and medullary thyroid carcinoma 1, Hirschsprung disease)
- RPP30: ribonuclease P protein subunit p30
- RRP12: ribosomal RNA processing 12 homolog
- RSU1: ras suppressor protein 1
- RTKN2: encoding protein Rhotekin 2
- SCZD11: encoding protein Schizophrenia susceptibility locus, chromosome 10q-related
- SGPL1: sphingosine-1-phosphate lyase 1
- SHTN1: encoding protein Shootin 1
- SLC16A12: encoding protein Solute carrier family 16 member 12
- SMNDC1: survival motor neuron domain containing 1
- SPG9 encoding protein Spastic paraplegia 9 (autosomal dominant)
- SRGN: serglycin
- STAMBPL1: STAM binding protein like 1
- STOX1: encoding protein Storkhead box 1
- SUFU: suppressor of fused protein

- SUPV3L1: Suv3 like RNA helicase
- SYCE1: encoding protein Synaptonemal complex central element protein 1
- TACC2 encoding protein Transforming acidic coiled-coil-containing protein 2
- TBC1D12: TBC1 domain family, member 12
- TCTN3: tectonic family member 3
- TMEM10: opalin
- TMEM254: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 254
- TMEM26: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 26
- TMEM72: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 72
- TYSND1: encoding protein Trypsin domain containing 1
- UCN3: urocortin-3
- UROS: uroporphyrinogen III synthase (congenital erythropoietic porphyria)
- USMG5: Up-regulated during skeletal muscle growth protein 5
- USP54: encoding protein Ubiquitin specific peptidase 54
- USP6NL: USP6 N-terminal like protein
- UTF1: undifferentiated embryonic cell transcription factor 1
- VIM-AS1: VIM antisense RNA 1
- WASHC2C: WASH complex subunit 2C
- WBP1L: WW domain binding protein 1-like
- ZNF37A: zinc finger protein 37A
- ZNF438: zinc finger protein 438
- ZRANB1: Zinc finger ranbp2-type containing 1

Diseases and disorders

- Apert syndrome
- Barakat syndrome
- Beare–Stevenson cutis gyrata syndrome
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease
- Cockayne syndrome
- Congenital erythropoietic porphyria
- Cowden syndrome
- Crouzon syndrome
- Genitopatellar syndrome
- Glioblastoma multiforme
- Gorlin syndrome
- HADDS syndrome
- Hermansky–Pudlak syndrome
- Hirschprung disease
- Jackson–Weiss syndrome
- Multiple endocrine neoplasia type 2
- Nonsyndromic deafness
- Pfeiffer syndrome
- Porphyria
- Spondyloepimetaphyseal dysplasia, Pakistani type
- Tetrahydrobiopterin deficiency
- Thiel–Behnke corneal dystrophy
- Usher syndrome
- Wolman syndrome
- Young-Simpson syndrome

chromosomes 11

Gene list

- ACAT1: acetyl-Coenzyme A acetyltransferase 1 (acetoacetyl Coenzyme A thiolase)
- ACRV1: encoding protein Acrosomal protein SP-10
- AKIP1: A kinase interacting protein 1
- ALKBH3 encoding protein AlkB homolog 3, alpha-ketoglutaratedependent dioxygenase
- AMOTL1: angiomin-like protein 1

- AMPD3: encoding enzyme AMP deaminase 3
- API5: encoding protein Apoptosis inhibitor 5
- APLNR: Apelin receptor (APJ receptor)
- APOA4: apolipoprotein A-IV
- ARCN1 encoding protein Archain 1
- ART5: encoding protein Adp-ribosyltransferase 5
- ASRGL1: encoding enzyme L-asparaginase
- ATM: ataxia telangiectasia mutated (includes complementation groups A, C and D)
- B3GNT1: encoding enzyme N-acetyllactosaminide beta-1,3-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase
- BATF2: encoding protein Basic leucine zipper transcription factor, ATF-like 2
- BDNF: secretes BDNF, a member of the Neurotrophin family of proteins
- C11orf1: encoding protein
- C11orf16: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein C11orf16
- C11orf49: encoding protein UPF0705 protein C11orf49
- C11orf52 encoding protein C11orf52
- C11orf53: encoding protein Chromosome 11 open reading frame 53
- C11orf54: encoding protein Ester hydrolase C11orf54
- C11orf80: encoding protein Chromosome 11 open reading frame 80
- C11orf86: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein C11orf86
- C1QTNF4 encoding protein C1q and tumor necrosis factor related protein 4
- C1QTNF5: encoding protein C1q and tumor necrosis factor related protein 5
- CAPRIN1: encoding protein, cell cycle associated protein 1
- CCDC88B: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 88b
- CCDC90B: coiled coil domain containing 90B
- CCL9: Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 9
- CD81: cluster of differentiation 81
- CDHR5: cadherin related family member 5
- CLDN25: encoding protein Claudin 25
- COMMD9: COMM domain-containing protein 9
- CPSF7: Cleavage and polyadenylation specificity factor subunit 7
- CPT1A: carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1A (liver)
- CREBZF encoding protein CREB/ATF bZIP transcription factor
- DAK: Triokinase/FMN cyclase
- DDI1: encoding protein DNA-damage inducible 1 homolog 1 (*S. cerevisiae*)
- DGAT2 encoding protein Diacylglycerol O-acyltransferase 2
- DHCR7: 7-dehydrocholesterol reductase
- DKK3: Dickkopf-related protein 3
- DPF2: Double PHD fingers 2
- DRD4: Dopamine receptor D4 at 11p15.5
- DSCAML1: encoding protein Down syndrome cell adhesion molecule like 1
- EI24: Etoposide-induced protein 2.4 homolog
- FAM118B: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 118, member B
- FAM76B: Family with sequence similarity 76 member B
- FAR1: fatty acyl-coA reductase 1

- FAT3: fat atypical cadherin 3
- FHIP: FTS and Hook-interacting protein
- FNBP4: Formin-binding protein 4
- FOLR3: encoding protein Folate receptor gamma
- GLB1L3: galactosidase, beta 1-like 3
- GLYAT: Glycine-N-acyltransferase
- GLYATL2 encoding protein Glycine-N-acyltransferase like 2
- GPHA2: Glycoprotein hormone alpha-2
- GYLTL1B: Glycosyltransferase-like protein LARGE2
- HBB: hemoglobin, beta
- HBBP1: encoding protein Hemoglobin, beta pseudogene 1
- HIKESH1: chromosome 11, open reading frame 73
- HMBS: hydroxymethylbilane VIIA
- HRASLS3: adipose phospholipase A2
- HTATIP2: HIV-1 Tat interactive protein 2
- HYLS1: Hydroletalus (Finnish heritage disease) related gene
- HYOU1: hypoxia upregulated protein 1
- IFITM2 encoding protein Interferon induced transmembrane protein 2
- IFT46: intraflagellar transport protein 46 homolog
- IGF2-AS: encoding protein IGF2 antisense RNA
- INS: insulin gene ^[11]
- KDM2A: lysine demethylase 2A
- KIAA1549L encoding protein KIAA1549-like
- KRTAP5-6: encoding protein Keratin associated protein 5-6
- LPXN: leupaxin
- LRFN4 encoding protein Leucine rich repeat and fibronectin type III domain containing 4
- MADD: MAP kinase-activating death domain protein
- MEN1: Multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1
- MIR210: encoding protein MicroRNA 210
- MIRLET7A2: microRNA let-7a-2
- MMP7: Matrix metalloproteinases (MMP family)
- MOGAT2: monoacylglycerol O-acyltransferase 2
- MTRNR2L8: encoding protein MT-RNR2-like 8
- NADSYN1: NAD synthetase 1
- NAP1L4: nucleosome assembly protein 1-like 4
- NFRKB: nuclear factor related to kappa-B binding protein
- NNMT: nicotinamide N-methyltransferase
- NRGN: neurogranin
- OR2AG2: encoding protein Olfactory receptor family 2 subfamily ag member 2
- P53AIP1: p53-regulated apoptosis-inducing protein 1
- PANO1: encoding protein PANO1
- PAX6: paired box 6
- PCNX3 encoding protein Pecanex homolog 3
- PGA3 encoding protein Pepsinogen 3, group I (pepsinogen A)

- PWIL4: encoding protein Piwi like RNA-mediated gene silencing 4
- PLET1: encoding protein Placenta expressed transcript 1
- PRR5L: proline rich 5 like
- PTPRCAP: protein tyrosine phosphatase receptor type C associated protein
- PTS: 6-pyruvoyltetrahydropterin synthase
- QSER1: glutamine serine rich protein 1
- RAG1/RAG2: recombination activating genes
- RASSF7: encoding protein Ras association domain family member 7
- RASSF10: encoding protein Ras association domain family member 10
- RELT: tumor necrosis factor receptor
- REXO2: RNA exonuclease 2
- RNH1: ribonuclease inhibitor 1
- RNU2-2: encoding protein RNA, U2 small nuclear 2
- ROM1: retinal outer segment membrane protein 1
- RPL27A: encoding protein 60S ribosomal protein L27a
- RPL36A: encoding protein 60S ribosomal protein L36a
- RSF1: remodeling and spacing factor 1
- SAA1: serum amyloid A1
- SAA2: serum amyloid A2
- SAC3D1: SAC3 domain-containing protein 1
- SART1: squamous cell carcinoma antigen recognized by T-cells 1
- SBF2: SET binding factor 2
- SCGB1D2: secretoglobin family 1D member 2
- SESN3: encoding protein Sestrin 3
- SIDT2: encoding protein SID1 transmembrane family member 2
- SLC17A6: encoding protein Solute carrier family 17 (vesicular glutamate transporter), member 6
- SLC25A22: encoding protein Solute carrier family 25 member 22
- SMAP1: small acidic protein
- SMCO4: encoding protein SMCO4
- SMPD1: sphingomyelin phosphodiesterase 1, acid lysosomal (acid sphingomyelinase)
- SNHG1: encoding protein Small nucleolar rna host gene 1
- SPA17: sperm autoantigenic protein 17
- SRPRA: Srp receptor alpha subunit
- Suppression of tumorigenicity 2: encoding protein Suppression of tumorigenicity 2
- TAF1D: TATA box binding protein associated factor RNA polymerase 1 subunit D
- TALDO1: encoding protein Transaldolase 1
- TBRG1: transforming growth factor beta regulator 1
- TECTA: tectorin alpha (nonsyndromic deafness)
- TH: tyrosine hydroxylase
- THRSP: thyroid hormone inducible hepatic protein
- THYN1: thymocyte nuclear protein 1
- TIMM10: translocase of inner mitochondrial membrane 10
- TIMM10B: Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit Tim9 B
- TM7SF2: transmembrane 7 superfamily member 2

- [TMEM109](#): encoding protein Transmembrane protein 109
- [TMEM123](#): transmembrane protein 123
- [TMEM126B](#): transmembrane protein 126B
- [TMEM134](#): transmembrane protein 134
- [TMEM25](#): transmembrane protein 25
- [TMPRSS4](#): encoding protein Transmembrane protease, serine 4
- [TP53I11](#): tumor protein 53 inducible protein 11
- [TRAPPC4](#): trafficking protein particle complex subunit 4
- [TRIM34](#): encoding protein Tripartite motif containing 34
- [TRPT1](#): tRNA 2'-phosphotransferase 1
- [UNC93B1](#): Unc-93 homolog B1
- [UPK2](#): uroplakin-2
- [UQCC3](#): encoding protein Ubiquinol-cytochrome c reductase complex assembly factor 3
- [USH1C](#): Usher syndrome 1C (autosomal recessive, severe)
- [USP47](#): ubiquitin specific peptidase 47
- [UVRAG](#): UV radiation resistance associated
- [VPS26B](#): vacuolar protein sorting 26 homolog B
- [VSIG2](#): V-set and immunoglobulin domain containing 2
- [WT1](#): Wilms tumor protein
- [YIF1A](#): Yip1 interacting factor homolog A
- [ZFP91-CNTF](#)
- [ZNF408](#): zinc finger protein 408

Diseases and disorders

- [autism \(NRXN2\)](#)
- [acute intermittent porphyria](#)
- [albinism](#)
- [ataxia–telangiectasia](#)
- [Beckwith–Wiedemann syndrome](#)
- [Best's disease](#)
- [beta-ketothiolase deficiency](#)
- [beta thalassemia](#)
- [bipolar disorder](#)
- [bladder cancer](#)
- [breast cancer](#)
- [carnitine palmitoyltransferase I deficiency](#)
- [Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease](#)
- [Cystic fibrosis](#)
- [Depression](#)
- [Denys–Drash syndrome](#)
- [familial Mediterranean fever](#)
- [Hereditary angioedema](#)
- [Jacobsen syndrome](#)
- [Jervell and Lange-Nielsen syndrome](#)
- [Mantle cell lymphoma \(t11;14\)](#)
- [Meckel syndrome](#)
- [methemoglobinemia, beta-globin type](#)
- [Mixed lineage leukemia](#)
- [multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1](#)
- [Hereditary multiple exostoses](#)
- [Nestor-Guillermo progeria syndrome](#)
- [Niemann–Pick disease](#)
- [nonsyndromic deafness](#)
- [porphyria](#)
- [Potocki–Shaffer syndrome](#)
- [Romano–Ward syndrome](#)
- [Sickle cell anemia](#)
- [Smith–Lemli–Opitz syndrome](#)

chromosomes 12

Gene list

- ACAD10: encoding protein Acyl-CoA dehydrogenase family, member 10
- ACSS3: encoding protein Acyl-CoA synthetase short-chain family member 3
- ACVRL1: activin A receptor type II-like 1f
- ANKRD33: encoding protein Ankyrin repeat domain 33
- APOF: encoding protein Apolipoprotein F
- APOLD1: apolipoprotein L domain containing 1
- ARL6IP4: encoding protein ADP-ribosylation-like factor 6 interacting protein 4
- ARPC3: encoding protein Actin-related protein 2/3 complex subunit 3

- Asun: encoding protein Protein asunder homolog (Asun)
- ATP2B1-AS1: encoding protein Atp2b1 antisense ma 1
- ATG101: Autophagy-related protein 101
- BCAT1: encoding protein Branched chain amino acid transaminase 1
- C12orf24: encoding protein FAM216A
- C12orf42: encoding protein uncharacterised chromosome 12 open reading frame 42
- C12orf43: encoding protein. Uncharacterized.
- C12orf60: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein C12orf60
- CALCOCO1: Calcium-binding and coiled-coil domain-containing protein 1
- CBX5: chromobox homolog 5
- CCDC53: Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 53
- CKAP4: Cytoskeleton associated protein 4
- CNOT2: encoding protein CCR4-NOT transcription complex subunit 2
- CNPY2: encoding protein Canopy FGF signaling regulator 2
- CCDC42B: encoding protein Coiled Coil Domain Containing protein 42B
- COL2A1: collagen, type II, alpha 1 (primary osteoarthritis, spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia, congenital)
- CRACR2A: encoding protein Calcium release activated channel regulator 2A
- CSRP2: Cysteine and glycine-rich protein 2
- DDX23: DEAD-box helicase 23
- DDX47: DEAD-box helicase 47
- DHH: Desert hedgehog protein
- DPPA3: Developmental pluripotency-associated protein 3
- DPY19L2: encoding protein Dpy-19-like 2 (C. elegans)
- E2F7: E2F transcription factor 7
- EMP1: Epithelial membrane protein 1
- ERGIC2: encoding protein a protein of 377 amino acid residues
- FAM60A: encoding protein FAM60A
- FAM186B: encoding protein Protein FAM186B
- GABARAPL1: encoding protein Gaba type a receptor associated protein like 1
- GPD1: encoding protein Glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1
- GOLT1B: Golgi transport 1B
- GPN3: encoding enzyme GPN-loop GTPase 3
- HNF1A-AS1: encoding protein HNF1A antisense RNA 1
- HPD: 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate dioxygenase
- IFFO1: encoding protein Intermediate filament family orphan 1
- KANSL2: encoding protein KAT8 regulatory NSL complex subunit 2 (KANSL2)
- KCNA1: potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 1 at 12p13.32
- KDM2B: encoding protein Lysine (K)-specific demethylase 2B
- KERA: keratocan
- KRAS: V-Ki-ras2 Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog
- LARP4: encoding protein La-related protein 4
- LEPREL2: encoding enzyme Prolyl 3-hydroxylase 3
- LMBR1L: encoding protein Protein LMBR1L
- LRRC23: encoding protein Leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 23

- LRR1Q1: encoding protein Leucine-rich repeats and IQ motif containing 1
- LRRK2: leucine-rich repeat kinase 2
- MBOAT5: encoding enzyme Lysophospholipid acyltransferase 5
- METTL1: encoding enzyme tRNA (guanine-N(7)-)-methyltransferase
- MFAP5: encoding protein Microfibrillar-associated protein 5
- MIR196A2: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 196a-2
- MMAB: methylmalonic aciduria (cobalamin deficiency) cblB type
- MON2: encoding protein Protein MON2 homolog
- MUCL1: encoding protein Mucin-like protein 1
- MYO1A: myosin IA
- NANOG: NK-2 type homeodomain gene
- NAP1L1: encoding protein Nucleosome assembly protein 1-like 1
- NRIP2: encoding protein Nuclear receptor-interacting protein 2
- NUDT4: encoding enzyme Diphosphoinositol polyphosphate phosphohydrolase 2
- PAH: phenylalanine hydroxylase
- PIP4K2C: encoding protein Phosphatidylinositol-5-phosphate 4-kinase, type II, gamma
- PWIL1: encoding protein Piwi-like protein 1
- PLBD1: encoding protein Phospholipase B domain containing 1 1
- POP5: encoding enzyme Ribonuclease P/MRP protein subunit POP5
- PPHLN1: encoding protein Periphilin-1
- PPP1R12A: protein phosphatase 1, regulatory (inhibitor) subunit 12A
- PRB1: encoding protein Basic salivary proline-rich protein 1
- PRB3: encoding protein Basic salivary proline-rich protein 3
- PRB4: encoding protein Basic salivary proline-rich protein 4
- PRH1: encoding protein Salivary acidic proline-rich phosphoprotein 1/2
- PRH2: encoding protein Proline-rich protein Haell subfamily 2
- PRMT8: encoding protein Protein arginine methyltransferase 8
- PRR4: encoding protein Proline-rich protein 4
- PTMS: encoding protein Parathyrosin
- PTPN11: protein tyrosine phosphatase, non-receptor type 11 (Noonan syndrome 1)
- PUS1: encoding enzyme tRNA pseudouridine synthase A
- PUS7L: encoding enzyme Pseudouridylate synthase 7 homolog-like protein
- PZP: encoding protein Pregnancy zone protein
- RAB3IP: encoding protein RAB3A-interacting protein
- RASSF8: encoding protein Ras association domain-containing protein 8
- RASSF9: encoding protein Ras association domain-containing protein 9
- RERG: encoding protein RAS-like, estrogen-regulated, growth inhibitor
- RNF34: encoding enzyme E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase RNF34
- SARNP: SAP domain-containing ribonucleoprotein
- Serpina3f: encoding protein Serine (or cysteine) peptidase inhibitor, clade A, member 3F
- SHMT2: encoding protein Serine hydroxymethyltransferase 2
- SLC8B1: solute carrier family 8 member B1
- TBC1D15: encoding protein TBC1 domain family member 15
- TBX3: encoding protein T-box transcription factor 3

- TCHP: encoding protein Trichoplein keratin filament-binding protein
- TESPA1: encoding protein Thymocyte expressed, positive selection associated 1
- THAP2: encoding protein THAP domain-containing protein 2
- TMTC1: encoding protein Transmembrane and tetratricopeptide repeat containing 1
- TMEM117: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 117
- TRAFD1: encoding protein TRAF-type zinc finger domain-containing protein 1
- TSFM: encoding protein Elongation factor Ts, mitochondrial
- TWF1: twinfilin-1
- UNQ1887:
- USP52: encoding enzyme PAB-dependent poly(A)-specific ribonuclease subunit 2
- UTP20: encoding protein Small subunit processome component 20 homolog
- VEZT: encoding protein Vezatin
- YAF2: encoding protein YY1-associated factor 2
- ZCCHC8: encoding protein Zinc finger CCHC domain-containing protein 8
- ZFC3H1: encoding protein Zinc finger C3H1-type containing
- ZNF26: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 26
- ZNF84: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 84
- ZNF268: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 268
- ZNF664: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 664

Diseases and disorders

- achondrogenesis type 2
- bipolar disorder
- collagenopathy, types II and XI
- cornea plana 2
- episodic ataxia
- hereditary hemorrhagic telangiectasia
- hypochondrogenesis
- ichthyosis bullosa of Siemens
- Kniest dysplasia
- Kabuki syndrome
- maturity onset diabetes of the young type 3
- methylmalonic acidemia
- narcolepsy
- nonsyndromic deafness
- Noonan syndrome
- Parkinson disease
- Pallister-Killian syndrome (tetrasomy 12p)
- phenylketonuria
- schizophrenia
- spondyloepimetaphyseal dysplasia, Strudwick type
- spondyloepiphyseal dysplasia congenita
- spondyloperipheral dysplasia
- Stickler syndrome, (COL2A1-related)
- Stuttering
- Triose Phosphate Isomerase deficiency
- tyrosinemia
- Von Willebrand Disease

chromosomes 13

Gene list

- ARGLU1: encoding protein Arginine and glutamate-rich protein 1
- ATP7B: ATPase, Cu⁺⁺ transporting, beta polypeptide (Wilson disease)
- BRCA2: breast cancer 2, early onset
- BRCA3 encoding protein Breast cancer 3
- C13orf42: encoding protein C13orf42
- CAB39L: encoding protein Calcium-binding protein 39-like
- CARKD: Carbohydrate Kinase Domain Containing Protein (Unknown Function)
- CCDC70: Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 70
- CHAMP1: Chromosome alignment-maintaining phosphoprotein 1
- CKAP2: Cytoskeleton-associated protein 2

- CLYBL: Citrate lyase beta like
- CRYL1: encoding protein Crystallin, lambda 1
- DLEU1: a long non-coding RNA
- DLEU2: Deleted in lymphocytic leukemia 1
- DZIP1: DAZ interacting zinc finger protein 1
- EDNRB: endothelin receptor type B
- ELF1: encoding protein E74-like factor 1 (ets domain transcription factor)
- ESD: S-formylglutathione hydrolase
- FAM155A: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 155, member A
- FLT1: Fms related tyrosine kinase 1 (Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 1)
- GJB2: gap junction protein, beta 2, 26kDa (connexin 26)
- GJB6: gap junction protein, beta 6 (connexin 30)
- Glypican 5: encoding protein Glypican-5
- HTR2A: 5-HT_{2A} receptor
- INTS6: encoding protein Integrator complex subunit 6
- GPALPP1: encoding protein KIAA1704
- L1TD1P1: encoding protein LINE-1 type transposase domain containing 1 pseudogene 1
- LACC1: encoding protein Laccase (multicopper oxidoreductase) domain containing 1
- LHFP: encoding protein Lipoma HMGIC fusion partner
- LINC00327: encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 327
- LINC00346: encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 346
- LOC107984557 encoding protein Methylcytosine dioxygenase TET1-like
- MBNL2: encoding protein Muscleblind-like protein 2
- MIPEP: encoding enzyme Mitochondrial intermediate peptidase
- MIRH1: encoding protein Putative microRNA host gene 1 protein
- MTRF1:
- NDFIP2: encoding protein NEDD4 family-interacting protein 2
- NUPL1: encoding protein Nucleoporin p58/p45
- POMP: encoding proteasome maturation protein
- PCCA: propionyl Coenzyme A carboxylase, alpha polypeptide
- RB1: retinoblastoma 1 (including osteosarcoma)
- RCBTB1: encoding protein RCC1 and BTB domain-containing protein 1
- RCBTB2: encoding protein RCC1 and BTB domain-containing protein 2
- RGCC: encoding protein Regulator of cell cycle RGCC
- RNR1: encoding RNA, ribosomal 45S cluster 1
- SCEL: encoding protein Sciellin
- SLC46A3: encoding protein Solute carrier family 46, member 3
- SLITRK1: encoding protein SLIT and NTRK-like protein 1
- SLITRK1: mutation in this gene causes some (although very few) cases of Tourette syndrome and trichotillomania
- SLITRK5: encoding protein SLIT and NTRK-like protein 5
- SLITRK6: encoding protein SLIT and NTRK-like protein 6
- SOX21: Transcription factor SOX-21 is a protein that in humans is encoded by the SOX21; its disruption can lead to types of alopecia in mice.

- SPRYD7: encoding protein SPRY domain-containing protein 7
- SUPT20H: SPT20 homolog
- TDRD3: encoding protein Tudor domain-containing protein 3
- TM9SF2: encoding protein Transmembrane 9 superfamily member 2
- TPT1: Translationally controlled tumor protein (TCTP)
- TSC22D1: encoding protein TSC22 domain family protein 1
- UBL3: encoding protein Ubiquitin-like protein 3
- WBP4: encoding protein WW domain-binding protein 4
- XPO4: encoding protein Exportin-4
- ZC3H13: encoding protein Zinc finger CCCH domain-containing protein 13
- ZMYM2: encoding protein Zinc finger MYM-type protein 2

Diseases and disorders

- 13q deletion syndrome
- Bipolar disorder
- Bladder cancer
- Breast cancer
- Heterochromia
- Hirschsprung's disease
- Maturity onset diabetes of the young type 4
- Nonsyndromic deafness
- Propionic acidemia
- Retinoblastoma
- Schizophrenia
- Waardenburg syndrome
- Wilson's disease
- Patau syndrome
- Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (Acquired defect)
- Young–Madders syndrome

chromosomes 14

Gene list

- ACIN1: encoding protein Apoptotic chromatin condensation inducer in the nucleus
- AHNAK2: encoding protein Ahnak nucleoprotein 2
- ATXN3: Ataxin-3 (Machado-Joseph disease)
- BCL2L2: encoding the anti-apoptotic protein Bcl-w of the Bcl-2 family
- C14orf80: encoding protein C14orf80
- C14orf93: encoding protein C14orf93
- CCDC176: encoding protein Basal body-orientation factor 1
- CCDC88C: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 88C
- CDC42BPB: encoding protein CDC42 binding protein kinase beta

- CDKL1: encoding protein Cyclin dependent kinase like 1
- CHMP4A: Charged multivesicular body protein 4a
- CIDEB: Cell death-inducing DFFA-like effector b
- CLBA1: encoding protein CLBA1
- CMA1: encoding enzyme Chymase
- CNIH: encoding protein Protein cornichon homolog
- COCH: coagulation factor C homolog, cochlin (*Limulus polyphemus*)
- CRIP2: Cysteine-rich protein 2
- DDX24: encoding enzyme ATP-dependent RNA helicase DDX24
- DEGS2: encoding protein Delta(4)-desaturase, sphingolipid 2
- DLGAP5: Disks large-associated protein 5
- DGLUCY: encoding protein DGLUCY, mitochondrial
- EAPP: E2F-associated phosphoprotein
- EGLN3: Egl nine homolog 3
- ENTPD5: Ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 5
- ERG28: encoding protein Probable ergosterol biosynthetic protein 28
- Fam158a: encoding protein UPF0172 protein FAM158A
- FAM181A: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 181, member A
- FAM71D: Family With Sequence Similarity 71, Member D
- FCF1: rRNA-processing protein FCF1 homolog
- FSCB: encoding protein Fibrous sheath CABYR binding protein
- GALC: galactosylceramidase (Krabbe disease)
- GARNL1: GTPase-activating Rap/Ran-GAP domain-like 1
- GCH1: GTP cyclohydrolase 1 (dopa-responsive dystonia)
- GPHB5: Glycoprotein hormone beta-5
- GSKIP encoding protein GSK3B interacting protein
- HHIPL1: encoding protein HHIP-like protein 1
- IFI27: encoding protein Interferon alpha-inducible protein 27
- IFT43: intraflagellar transport 43
- IGH@: immunoglobulin heavy chain locus
- IRF2BPL: encoding protein Interferon regulatory factor 2 binding protein like
- ITPK1: encoding enzyme Inositol-tetrakisphosphate 1-kinase
- JKAMP: encoding protein JNK1-associated membrane protein
- JPH4: encoding protein Junctophilin 4
- LINC00520: a long non-coding RNA
- LINC00637: encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 637
- MAPK1IP1L: encoding protein MAPK-interacting and spindle-stabilizing protein-like
- MIA2: encoding protein Melanoma inhibitory activity protein 2
- MIR494 encoding protein MicroRNA 494
- MIR495: encoding protein MicroRNA 495
- MIR3173: encoding protein MicroRNA 3173
- MIS18BP1: encoding protein MIS18 binding protein 1
- MOAP1: encoding protein Modulator of apoptosis 1
- MYH7: myosin heavy chain beta (MHC- β) isoform^[11]

- NEMF (gene): encoding protein Nuclear export mediator factor
- NPC2: Niemann-Pick disease, type C2
- NUBPL: encoding protein Iron-sulfur protein NUBPL (IND1)
- OSGEP: encoding enzyme Probable O-sialoglycoprotein endopeptidase
- PAPOLA: encoding enzyme Poly(A) polymerase alpha
- PCNX: encoding protein Pecanex-like protein 1
- PELI2: encoding protein Protein pellino homolog 2
- PLEKHG3: encoding protein Pleckstrin homology and rhogef domain containing g3
- PSEN1: presenilin 1 (Alzheimer disease 3)
- RIOX1: encoding protein RIOX1
- RTRAF: encoding protein RTRAF
- RPL10L: encoding protein 60S ribosomal protein L10-like
- SERPINA1: serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade A (alpha-1 antiproteinase, antitrypsin), member 1
- SERPINA3: encoding protein alpha-1-antichymotrypsin (ACT)
- SERPINA12: encoding protein SERPINA12
- SIX6OS1: encoding protein SIX6OS1
- SGPP1: encoding enzyme Sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 1
- SNORD9: encoding protein Small nucleolar rna, c/d box 9
- SYNE3: encoding protein Spectrin repeat containing nuclear envelope family member
- TC2N: encoding protein Tandem C2 domains nuclear protein
- TCL1B: encoding protein T-cell leukemia/lymphoma protein 1B
- TIMM9: encoding enzyme Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit Tim9
- TMED10: encoding protein Transmembrane emp24 domain-containing protein 10
- TMEM260: encoding protein TMEM260
- TRAJ56: encoding protein T cell receptor alpha joining 56
- TRAV12-2: encoding protein T cell receptor alpha variable 12-2
- TSHR: thyroid stimulating hormone receptor
- TUNAR: a long non-coding RNA
- VASH1: encoding protein Vasohibin-1
- VIPAS39: encoding protein VIPAS39
- WARS: encoding enzyme Tryptophanyl-tRNA synthetase, cytoplasmic
- YLPM1: encoding protein YLP motif-containing protein 1
- ZBTB1: encoding protein Zinc finger and BTB domain containing 1
- ZFHX2: encoding protein Zinc finger homeobox 2
- ZNF839: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 839

Diseases and disorders

- | | |
|---|---|
| ▪ <u>Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency</u> | ▪ <u>Follicular lymphoma (t14;18)</u> |
| ▪ <u>Alzheimer disease</u> | ▪ <u>FOXG1 Syndrome</u> |
| ▪ <u>Burkitt's lymphoma (t8;14)</u> | ▪ <u>Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy</u> |
| ▪ <u>congenital hypothyroidism</u> | ▪ <u>Krabbe disease</u> |
| ▪ <u>dopamine-responsive dystonia</u> | ▪ <u>Cranio-lenticulo-sutural dysplasia</u> |

- Machado-Joseph disease
- Mosaic monosomy 14
- Multiple myeloma
- Niemann-Pick disease
- Nonsyndromic deafness
- Sensenbrenner syndrome
- Tetrahydrobiopterin deficiency
- Uniparental disomy (UPD) 14
- Oculopharyngeal muscular dystrophy

chromosomes 15

Gene list

- AAGAB: alpha- and gamma-adaptin binding protein
- ACSBG1: encoding enzyme Acyl-CoA Synthetase, Bubblegum Family, member 1
- ADH1: alcohol dehydrogenase
- ARHGAP11B: a human-specific gene encoding the Rho GTPase activating protein 11B, that amplifies basal progenitors, controls neural progenitor proliferation, and contributes to neocortex folding.

- ARPIN: encoding protein Actin related protein 2/3 complex inhibitor
- ARPP-19: encoding protein cAMP-regulated phosphoprotein 19
- B2MR: encoding protein Beta-2-microglobulin regulator
- C15orf15: encoding protein Probable ribosome biogenesis protein RLP24
- C15orf32: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein C15orf32
- C15orf54: encoding protein Chromosome 15 Open Reading Frame 54
- CAPN3: Calpain 3 (limb-girdle muscular dystrophy type 2A)
- CELF6: encoding protein Cugbp elav-like family member 6
- CHP: Calcium binding protein P22\
- CHSY1: Chondroitin sulfate synthase 1
- CLK3: CDC like kinase 3
- ClpX: encoding enzyme ATP-dependent Clp protease ATP-binding subunit clpX-like, mitochondrial
- COMMD4: encoding protein COMM domain-containing protein 4
- CPEB1: Cytoplasmic polyadenylation element binding protein 1
- CRAT37: encoding protein Cervical cancer-associated transcript 37
- CYP19A1: encoding protein Cytochrome p450 family 19 subfamily a member 1
- DTWD1:
- ELL3: encoding protein Elongation factor RNA polymerase II-like 3
- FAH: fumarylacetoacetate hydrolase (fumarylacetoacetase)
- FAM214A: encoding protein Protein FAM214A
- FBN1: fibrillin 1 (Marfan syndrome)
- FOXB1: encoding protein Forkhead box B1
- GATM: Glycine aminotransferase, mitochondrial
- GCHFR: GTP cyclohydrolase 1 feedback regulatory protein
- GLC1I: encoding protein Glaucoma 1, open angle, i
- GLCE: D-glucuronyl C5-epimerase
- GOLGA8H: encoding protein Golgin subfamily A member 8H
- HDGFRP3:
- HEXA: hexosaminidase A (alpha polypeptide)(Tay–Sachs disease)
- HMG20A: encoding protein High mobility group protein 20A
- IDDM3 encoding protein Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus 3
- IMP3: encoding protein U3 small nucleolar ribonucleoprotein protein IMP3
- ITPKA: encoding enzyme Inositol-trisphosphate 3-kinase A
- MD: isovaleryl Coenzyme A dehydrogenase
- KATNBL1: encoding protein KATNBL1
- KIAA1024: encoding protein Kiaa1024
- LARP6 encoding protein La-related protein 6 also known as acheron or La ribonucleoprotein domain family member 6 (LARP6),
- LCMT2: encoding enzyme Leucine carboxyl methyltransferase 2
- LINC00926 encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 926
- MESDC2: encoding protein LDLR chaperone MESD
- MESP1: encoding protein Mesoderm posterior 1 homolog (mouse)
- MFAP1: encoding protein Microfibrillar-associated protein 1
- MCPH4: microcephaly, primary autosomal recessive 4

- MCTP2: encoding protein Multiple c2 domains, transmembrane 2
- MIR7-2: encoding protein MicroRNA 7-2
- MIR1282: encoding protein MicroRNA 1282
- MIR627: encoding protein MicroRNA 627
- MIR9-3HG: encoding protein MIR9-3 host gene
- NIPA2: encoding protein Non-imprinted in Prader-Willi/Angelman syndrome region protein 2
- NUSAP1: encoding protein Nucleolar and spindle associated protein 1
- OCA2: oculocutaneous albinism II (pink-eye dilution homolog, mouse)
- PDCD7: encoding protein Programmed cell death protein 7
- PIF1: encoding protein PIF1 5'-to-3' DNA helicase
- PIGBOS1: encoding protein Pigb opposite strand 1
- PLA2G4D: encoding protein Phospholipase A2 group IV D
- PLA2G4E: encoding protein Phospholipase A2 group IV E
- PML: promyelocytic leukemia protein (involved in t(15,17) with RARalpha, predominant cause of acute promyelocytic leukemia.
- POTEB: encoding protein POTE ankyrin domain family, member B
- PTPLAD1: encoding enzyme Protein tyrosine phosphatase-like protein PTPLAD1
- PYGO1: encoding protein Pygopus homolog 1 (Drosophila)
- RAD51: RAD51 homolog (RecA homolog, E. coli) (*S. cerevisiae*)
- RMDN3: encoding protein Regulator of microtubule dynamics protein 3
- RNR3: encoding RNA, ribosomal 45S cluster 3
- RTF1: encoding protein Rtf1, Paf1/RNA polymerase II complex component, homolog (*S. cerevisiae*)
- RTFDC1: encoding protein Replication termination factor 2
- SCAMP2: encoding protein Secretory carrier-associated membrane protein 2
- SCAMP5: encoding protein Secretory carrier-associated membrane protein 5
- SCZD10: encoding protein Schizophrenia disorder 10 (periodic catatonia)
- SCAPER: S-phase CyclinA Associated Protein residing in the Endoplasmic Reticulum
- SEN8: encoding enzyme Sentrin-specific protease 8
- SERF2: encoding protein Small EDRK-rich factor 2
- SLC24A5: the gene responsible for at least 1/3 of the skin color differences between races, expressed in the brain and the nervous system
- SNAPC5: encoding protein snRNA-activating protein complex subunit 5
- SPN1: encoding protein Snurportin1
- STRC: stereocilin
- SUHW4: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 280D
- SYNM: encoding protein Synemin
- TEX9: encoding protein Testis-expressed protein 9
- TGFBR2: location 3p24.2-p25 due to a inactivation mutation
- TMC3: encoding protein Transmembrane channel like 3
- TM6SF1: encoding protein Transmembrane 6 superfamily member 1
- TMCO5A: encoding protein Transmembrane and coiled-coil domains 5A
- TMED3: encoding protein Transmembrane p24 trafficking protein 3
- UBE2Q2: encoding protein Ubiquitin conjugating enzyme e2 q2
- UBE3A: ubiquitin protein ligase E3A (human papilloma virus E6-associated protein, Angelman syndrome)

- Ube3a-ATS:
- UNC13C: encoding protein Unc-13 homolog C
- VPS39: encoding protein hVam6p/Vps39-like protein
- WDR76: encoding protein Wd repeat domain 76
- ZNF592: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 592

Diseases and disorders

- Bloom syndrome
- Breast cancer
- Isovaleric acidemia
- Loeys–Dietz, type 3 (SMAD3 gene)
- Marfan syndrome
- Nonsyndromic deafness
- Schaaf–Yang syndrome (SYS)
- Tay–Sachs disease

chromosomes 16

Gene list

- ACSF3: encoding enzyme Acyl-CoA synthetase family member 3
- ACSM2B: encoding enzyme Acyl-coenzyme A synthetase ACSM2B, mitochondrial
- ACSM3: encoding enzyme Acyl-coenzyme A synthetase ACSM3, mitochondrial 2
- ADHD1: Attention deficit-hyperactivity disorder, susceptibility to, 1
- ARL6IP1: encoding protein ADP-ribosylation factor-like protein 6-interacting protein 1
- ARMC5
- BMIQ5: Body mass index quantitative trait locus 5
- C16orf58: encoding protein Chromosome 16 open reading frame 58
- C16orf71: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein Chromosome 16 Open Reading Frame 71
- C16orf82:

- C16orf84:
- C16orf95:
- C16orf96: encoding protein C16orf96, or chromosome 16 open reading frame 96,
- CARHSP1: Calcium-regulated heat stable protein 1
- CASP16P: encoding protein Caspase 16, pseudogene
- CCDC113: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 113
- Ccdc78: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain-containing 78 (CCDC78)
- CDIPT: CDP-diacylglycerol-inositol 3-phosphatidyltransferase
- CFDP1: Craniofacial development protein 1
- CHDS1: Coronary heart disease, susceptibility to, 1
- CIAPIN1: Anamorsin (originally, Cytokine induced apoptosis inhibitor 1)
- CKLF: Chemokine-like factor
- CLUAP1:
- CMTM2: encoding protein CKLF-like MARVEL transmembrane domain-containing protein 2
- CCDC135: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 135
- COTL1: encoding protein Coactosin-like protein
- CPNE7: encoding protein Copine 7
- CTRL: Chymotrypsin-like protease
- DCTPP1: encoding enzyme dCTP pyrophosphatase 1
- DEL16P12.1P11.2: Chromosome 16p12.2-p11.2 deletion syndrome
- DEL16p13.3, RSTSS: Chromosome 16p13.3 deletion syndrome (Rubinstein-Taybi deletion syndrome)
- DHX38: DEAH-box helicase 38
- DUP16p13.3, C16DUPq13.3: Chromosome 16p13.3 duplication syndrome
- EMP2: Epithelial membrane protein 2
- ENKD1: Enkurin domain-containing protein 1
- ERAF: Alpha-hemoglobin-stabilizing protein
- FAHD1: Fumarylacetoacetate hydrolase domain-containing protein 1
- FAM57B: Family with sequence similarity 57 member B
- FBRS: Probably fibrosin-1 long transcript protein
- FOXC2-AS1: encoding protein FOXC2 antisense RNA 1
- GLG1: Golgi apparatus protein 1
- HBAP1: Hemoglobin, alpha pseudogene 1
- HBHR, ATR1: Alpha-thalassemia/mental retardation syndrome, type 1
- HIRIP3: encoding protein HIRA-interacting protein 3
- HN1L: encoding protein Hematological and neurological expressed 1-like protein
- IBD8: Inflammatory bowel disease 8
- IHPS2: Pyloric stenosis, infantile hypertrophic, 2
- ITFG3: encoding protein Protein ITFG3
- KDM8: encoding protein Lysine demethylase 8
- KIAA0895L: uncharacterized protein KIAA0895-like
- LINC00273 encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 273
- LOC124220: encoding protein Zymogen granule protein 16 homolog B
- LOC81691:
- LUC7L: encoding protein Putative RNA-binding protein Luc7-like 1

- LYPLA3: encoding enzyme Group XV phospholipase A2
- MC1R: melanocortin 1 receptor
- MCOPCT1: Microphthalmia with cataract 1
- METRN: encoding protein Meteorin, glial cell differentiation regulator
- METTL26/JFP2: encoding protein Chromosome 16 open reading frame 13
- MKL2: encoding protein MKL/myocardin-like protein 2
- MPHOSPH6: encoding enzyme M-phase phosphoprotein 6
- MT1G: encoding protein Metallothionein-1G
- MT1X: encoding protein Metallothionein 1X
- NIP30: encoding protein NIP30 protein
- NOB1: encoding protein RNA-binding protein NOB1
- NOMO1: encoding protein Nodal modulator 1
- NPW: encoding protein Neuropeptide W
- NUBP2: encoding protein Nucleotide-binding protein 2
- NUPR1: encoding protein Nuclear protein 1
- OGFOD1:
- PDF: encoding enzyme Peptide deformylase, mitochondrial
- PDPR: encoding protein Pyruvate dehydrogenase phosphatase regulatory subunit
- PKDTS: Polycystic kidney disease, infantile severe, with tuberous sclerosis
- PMFBP1: encoding protein Polyamine-modulated factor 1-binding protein 1
- POLR3K: encoding enzyme DNA-directed RNA polymerase III subunit RPC10
- PRMT7: encoding protein Protein arginine methyltransferase 7
- PRR35: encoding protein Proline rich 35
- RPS15A: encoding protein 40S ribosomal protein S15a
- RSL1D1: encoding protein Ribosomal L1 domain-containing protein 1
- SHCBP1: encoding protein SHC SH2 domain-binding protein 1
- SLZ1: encoding protein SLX1 structure-specific endonuclease subunit homolog B (*S. cerevisiae*)
- SNAI3-AS1: encoding protein SNAI3 antisense RNA 1
- SNORD71: encoding protein Small nucleolar RNA, C/D box 71
- SPSB3: encoding protein SplA/ryanodine receptor domain and SOCS box containing 3
- SRCAP: encoding enzyme Helicase SRCAP
- TANGO6: encoding protein Transport and Golgi organization protein 6 homolog
- TAO2: encoding Serine/threonine-protein kinase TAO2
- TBC1D24: encoding protein TBC1 domain family, member 24
- TEDC2: encoding protein Tubulin epsilon and delta complex 2
- TELO2: encoding protein Telomere length regulation protein TEL2 homolog
- TMEM112: encoding enzyme Lipase maturation factor 1
- TMEM8A: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 8A
- TNRC6A: encoding protein Trinucleotide repeat-containing gene 6A protein
- Tuberous sclerosis complex tumor suppressors: encoding [[]] FALSE
- TSR3: encoding
- UNKL: encoding protein RING finger protein unkempt-like
- VAT1L: encoding protein Vesicle amine transport protein 1 homolog (*T. californica*)-like
- VPS35L: encoding protein VPS35 Endosomal Protein Sorting Factor Like

- WFDC1: encoding protein WAP four-disulfide core domain protein 1
- ZG16
- ZNF23: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 23
- ZNF200: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 200
- ZNF263: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 263
- ZNF629: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 629
- ZNF843: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 843

Diseases and disorders

- Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)
- Asperger syndrome
- Autism spectrum disorder
- Autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease (PKD-1)
- Batten disease
- Combined malonic and methylmalonic aciduria (CMAMMA)
- Familial Mediterranean fever (FMF)
- Synesthesia
- Thalassemia
- Trisomy 16

Chromosomes 17

Gene list

- [2700099C18Rik](#): encoding [protein NDC80 homolog](#), kinetochore complex component pseudogene
- [ABI3](#): encoding [protein ABI gene family member 3](#)
- [ABR](#): encoding [protein Abr, rhogef and gtpase activating protein](#)
- [ARHGAP44](#): encoding [protein Rho GTPase activating protein 44](#)
- [AZI1](#): encoding [protein 5-azacytidine-induced protein 1](#)
- [BRCA1P1](#): encoding [protein BRCA1 pseudogene 1](#)
- [BCPR](#) encoding [protein Breast cancer-related regulator of TP53](#)
- [C17orf98](#): encoding [protein C17orf98](#)
- [C1QL1](#): encoding [protein complement component 1, q subcomponent-like 1](#)
- [CCDC144A](#): encoding [protein Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 144A](#)

- CCDC40: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 40
- CCDC47: encoding protein CCDC47
- CCDC57: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 57
- CLUH: encoding protein Clustered mitochondria (cluA/CLU1) homolog
- CTDNEP1: encoding protein CTD nuclear envelope phosphatase 1
- DEL17P13.1 encoding protein Chromosome 17p13.1 deletion syndrome
- DHX8: encoding protein DEAH-box helicase 8
- DPH1 encoding protein Diphthamide biosynthesis protein 1
- DUP17Q12: encoding protein Chromosome 17q12 duplication syndrome
- FAM20A: encoding protein FAM20A
- GAS7: encoding protein Growth arrest-specific protein 7
- GGT6: encoding protein Gamma-glutamyltransferase 6
- HN1: encoding protein Hematological and neurological expressed 1 protein
- IBD22 encoding protein Inflammatory bowel disease-22
- KRTAP locus: encoding ca. 40 Keratin-associated proteins
- LINC00511: encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 511
- LINC00674 encoding protein Long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 674
- LRR37A encoding protein Leucine rich repeat containing 37A
- LRR48: encoding protein Leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 48
- MBTD1: encoding protein Malignant Brain Tumor domain containing 1
- METTL16: encoding protein Methyltransferase like 16
- MGAT5B: encoding enzyme Alpha-1,6-mannosylglycoprotein 6-beta-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase B
- MIR195: encoding protein MicroRNA 195
- MIR4521: encoding protein MicroRNA 4521
- MLLT6: encoding protein MLLT6, PHD finger containing
- MSI2: encoding protein Musashi RNA binding protein 2
- MYBBP1A: encoding protein Myb-binding protein 1A
- MYCBPAP: encoding protein MYCBP associated protein
- NBP: encoding peptide Neuropeptide B
- NME1-NME2:
- NXPH3: encoding protein Neurexophilin-3
- OMG: encoding protein Oligodendrocyte-myelin glycoprotein
- Ormdl sphingolipid biosynthesis regulator 3: encoding protein ORMDL sphingolipid biosynthesis regulator 3
- PLXDC1: encoding protein Plexin domain-containing protein 1
- PNPO: encoding enzyme Pyridoxine-5'-phosphate oxidase
- PPP1R27: encoding protein Protein phosphatase 1, regulatory subunit 27
- PRCD: encoding protein Progressive rod-cone degeneration
- PRPSAP2: encoding protein Phosphoribosyl pyrophosphate synthetase-associated protein 2
- PRR29: encoding protein Proline-rich protein 29
- QRICH2: encoding protein Glutamine-rich protein 2
- RAP1GAP2: encoding protein RAP1 GTPase activating protein 2
- RFFL: encoding enzyme E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase rififylin
- RNMTL1: encoding enzyme RNA methyltransferase-like protein 1
- RPAIN: encoding protein RPA-interacting protein

- RPL23A: encoding protein 60S ribosomal protein L23a
- SC65: encoding protein Synaptonemal complex protein SC65
- SCPEP1: encoding enzyme Retinoid-inducible serine carboxypeptidase
- SEBOX: encoding protein SEBOX homeobox
- SECTM1: encoding protein Secreted and transmembrane protein 1
- SEPTIN4: encoding Septin4
- SKA2: encoding protein Spindle and Kinetochore Associated
- SLC39A11: encoding protein Solute carrier family 39 member 11
- SLFN11: encoding protein Schlafen family member 11
- SLFN12: encoding protein Schlafen family member 12
- SNF8: encoding protein Vacuolar-sorting protein SNF8
- SPACA3: Sperm acrosome membrane-associated protein 3
- SPAG5: encoding protein Sperm-associated antigen 5
- ST6GALNAC1: encoding enzyme Alpha-N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 1
- ST6GALNAC2: encoding enzyme Alpha-N-acetylgalactosaminide alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 2
- STH: encoding protein Saitohin
- SUZ12P1 encoding protein SUZ12 polycomb repressive complex 2 subunit pseudogene 1
- TAC4: encoding protein Tachykinin-4
- TBC1D3: encoding protein TBC1 domain family member 3E/3F
- TMEM106A: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 106A
- TMEM98: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 98
- TNFSF12-TNFSF13:
- TOM1L1: encoding protein TOM1-like protein 1
- TOM1L2: encoding protein TOM1-like protein 2
- TRIM65: encoding protein Tripartite motif containing 65
- TRPV1: encoding protein Transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 1
- TSEN54: encoding protein TRNA splicing endonuclease subunit 54
- TTYH2: encoding protein Tweety family member 2
- VAT1: encoding protein Synaptic vesicle membrane protein VAT-1 homolog
- VPS25: encoding protein Vacuolar protein-sorting-associated protein 25
- VPS53: encoding protein Vacuolar protein sorting 53 homolog (S. cerevisiae)
- YBX2: encoding protein Y-box-binding protein 2
- ZNF207: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 207
- ZNF830: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 830
- Several CC chemokines: CCL1, CCL2, CCL3, CCL4, CCL5, CCL7, CCL8, CCL11, CCL13, CCL14, CCL15, CCL16, CCL18, and CCL23

The following are some of the genes and their corresponding Cytogenetic location on chromosome 17:

p-arm

- FLCN: folliculin (17p11.2)
- MYO15A: myosin XVA (17p11.2)
- RAI1: retinoic acid induced 1 (17p11.2)
- PMP22: peripheral myelin protein 22 (17p12)

- CTNS: cystinosis, the lysosomal cystine transporter (17p13)
- USP6: Ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase 6 linked to Aneurysmal bone cyst (17p13)
- ACADVL: acyl-coenzyme A dehydrogenase, very long chain (17p13.1)
- SHBG: Sex hormone binding globulin (17p13.1)
- TP53: tumor suppressor protein p53 (Li-Fraumeni syndrome), tumor suppressor gene (17p13.1)
- ASPA: aspartoacylase (Canavan disease) (17p13.3)
- GLOD4: glyoxalase domain containing 4 (17p13.3)

q-arm

- CCDC55: Coiled-coil domain-containing protein 55 (17q11.2)
- FLOT2: flotillin 2 (17q11.2)
- NF1: neurofibromin 1 (neurofibromatosis, von Recklinghausen disease, Watson disease) (17q11.2)
- SLC6A4: Serotonin transporter linked to Obsessive Compulsive Disorder (OCD) ^[11] (17q11.2)
- CCL4L1: C-C motif chemokine ligand 4 like 1 (17q12)
- DDX52: DExD-box helicase 52 (17q12)
- ERBB2 loca leukemia viral oncogene homolog 2, neuro/glioblastoma derived oncogene homolog (avian) (17q12)
- GRB7: Growth factor Receptor-Bound protein 7 (17q12)
- BRCA1: breast cancer 1, early onset (17q21)
- GFAP: glial fibrillary acidic protein (17q21)
- RARA or RAR-alpha: Retinoic acid receptor Alpha (involved in t(15,17) with PML) (17q21)
- MAPT gene coding for encoding tau protein (17q21.1)
- NAGLU: N-acetyl glucosaminidase, Sanfilippo B syndrome (17q21.2)
- SLC4A1: Band 3 anion transporter protein. Solute carrier family 4, member 1 (17q21.31)
- CBX1: chromobox homolog 1 (17q21.32)
- COL1A1: collagen, type I, alpha 1 (17q21.33)
- LUC7L3: LUC7 like 3 pre-mRNA splicing factor (17q21.33)
- NOG: Noggin protein (17q22)
- RPS6KB1 or S6K: Ribosomal protein S6-kinase (17q23.1)
- FTSJ3: FtsJ homolog 3 (17q23.3)
- SCN4A: Voltage-Gated Sodium Channel Subunit Alpha Nav1.4 (17q23.3)
- GALK1: galactokinase 1 (17q24)
- KCNJ2: potassium inwardly-rectifying channel, subfamily J, member 2 (17q24.3)
- ACTG1: actin, gamma 1 (17q25)
- CDC42EP4: CDC42 effector protein 4 (17q25.1)
- USH1G: Usher syndrome 1G (autosomal recessive) (17q25.1)
- CANT1: Calcium-activated nucleotidase 1 (17q25.3)
- BIRC5: Survivin (17q25.3)
- CHMP6: Charged multivesicular body protein 6 (17q25.3)
- ENPP7: ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 7 (17q25.3)
- EPR1: Effector cell peptidase receptor 1 (17q25.3)
- RHBDF2: Rhomboid family member 2 (17q25.3)
- TMC6 and TMC8: Transmembrane channel-like 6 and 8 (epidermodysplasia verruciformis) (17q25.3)

- WT4: encoding protein Wilms tumor-4

Diseases and disorders

- 17q12 microdeletion syndrome
- Koolen–de Vries syndrome
- Alexander disease
- Andersen–Tawil syndrome
- Aneurysmal bone cyst
- Bipolar disorder
- Birt–Hogg–Dubé syndrome
- Bladder cancer
- Breast cancer
- Bruck syndrome
- Campomelic dysplasia
- Canavan disease
- Cerebroretinal microangiopathy with calcifications and cysts
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease
- Chronic lymphocytic leukaemia, tp53
- Corticobasal degeneration
- Cystinosis
- Depression
- Ehlers–Danlos syndrome
- Epidermodysplasia verruciformis
- Frontotemporal dementia and parkinsonism linked to chromosome 17
- Galactosemia
- Glycogen storage disease type II (Pompe disease)
- Hereditary neuropathy with liability to pressure palsies
- Howel–Evans syndrome
- Li–Fraumeni syndrome
- Maturity onset diabetes of the young type 5
- Miller–Dieker syndrome
- Multiple synostoses syndrome
- Neurofibromatosis type I
- Nonsyndromic deafness
- Obsessive–compulsive disorder
- Osteogenesis imperfecta
- Potocki–Lupski syndrome
- Proximal symphalangism
- Sanfilippo syndrome
- Smith–Magenis syndrome
- Usher syndrome
- Very long-chain acyl-coenzyme A dehydrogenase deficiency

chromosomes 18

Gene list

- [ASXL3](#): encoding protein Additional sex combs like 3 (Drosophila)
- [C18orf63](#): encoding protein Chromosome 18 open reading frame 63
- [CABLES1](#): encoding protein CDK5 and ABL1 enzyme substrate 1
- [CABYR](#): Calcium-binding tyrosine phosphorylation-regulated protein
- [CHMP1B](#): Charged multivesicular body protein 1b
- [CXXC1](#): CXXC-type zinc finger protein 1
- [DCC](#): Deleted in Colorectal Cancer
- [DIPK1C](#): encoding protein Divergent protein kinase domain 1C
- [ELAC1](#): elaC ribonuclease Z 1
- [ESCO1](#): encoding protein Establishment of sister chromatid cohesion N-acetyltransferase 1

- FECH: ferrochelatase (protoporphyrin)
- GREB1L: encoding protein Growth regulation by estrogen in breast cancer-like
- HAUS1: HAUS augmin-like complex subunit 1
- HDHD2: encoding enzyme Haloacid dehalogenase-like hydrolase domain-containing protein 2
- IER3IP1: encoding protein Immediate early response 3-interacting protein 1
- MIR133A1: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 133a-1
- MIR187: encoding protein MicroRNA 187
- MRCL3: encoding protein Myosin regulatory light chain 12A
- NAPG: encoding protein Gamma-soluble NSF attachment protein
- NOL4: encoding protein Nucleolar protein 4
- NPC1: Niemann-Pick disease, type C1
- PIGN: encoding protein Phosphatidylinositol glycan anchor biosynthesis, class N
- PSTPIP2: encoding enzyme Proline-serine-threonine phosphatase-interacting protein 2
- RP11-267C16.1: non-coding
- SERPINB10: encoding protein Serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade B (ovalbumin), member 10
- SIGLEC15: encoding protein Sialic acid binding Ig-like lectin 15
- SMAD4: SMAD, mothers against DPP homolog 4 (Drosophila)
- TMEM241: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 241
- TTC39C: encoding protein Tetratricopeptide repeat protein 39C
- TWSG1: encoding protein Twisted gastrulation protein homolog 1
- ZCCHC2: encoding protein Zinc finger CCHC domain-containing protein 2
- ZFP161: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 161 homolog
- ZNF236: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 236
- ZNF516: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 516
- ZNF521: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 521
- ZNF532: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 532

Diseases and disorders

- Erythropoietic protoporphyria
- Hereditary hemorrhagic telangiectasia
- Niemann–Pick disease type C
- Porphyria
- Selective mutism
- Edwards syndrome (trisomy 18)
- Tetrasomy 18p
- Monosomy 18p
- Pitt–Hopkins syndrome 18q21
- Distal 18q- (distal deletion)

- Proximal 18q- (proximal deletion)

chromosomes 19

Gene list

- [A1BG](#): encoding [protein](#) Alpha-1-B glycoprotein
- [AAVS1](#), viral integration site
- [ACSBG2](#): encoding [enzyme](#) Long-chain-fatty-acid—CoA ligase
- [ANKRD24](#): encoding [protein](#) Ankyrin repeat domain-containing protein 24
- [ARMC6](#): encoding [protein](#) Armadillo repeat-containing protein 6
- [ATG4D](#): encoding [protein](#) Autophagy related 4D, cysteine peptidase
- [ATP5SL](#): encoding [protein](#) ATP synthase subunit s-like protein
- [ATPase ASNA1](#): encoding [enzyme](#) ATPase ASNA1 also known as arsenical pump-driving ATPase and arsenite-stimulated ATPase
- [BTBD14B](#): encoding [protein](#) Nucleus accumbens-associated protein 1
- [C19orf18](#): encoding [protein](#) Chromosome 19 open reading frame 18

- C19orf44: encoding protein Chromosome 19 open reading frame 44
- C19orf70: encoding protein Chromosome 19 open reading frame 70
- CACTIN: encoding protein Cactin
- CCDC130: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 130
- CCDC151: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 151
- CCDC8: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 8
- CCDC94: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 94 (CCDC94),
- CXB3S: encoding protein Coxsackie virus B3 sensitivity
- DHX34: encoding protein Dexh-box helicase 34
- DNASE2: encoding protein Deoxyribonuclease II, lysosomal
- DPF1: encoding protein D4, zinc and double PHD fingers family 1
- EID2:
- ETV2: encoding protein Ets variant 2
- FIZ1: encoding protein FLT3 interacting zinc finger 1
- HCST: encoding protein Hematopoietic cell signal transducer
- HRC: encoding protein Sarcoplasmic reticulum histidine-rich calcium-binding protein
- IFI30: encoding enzyme Gamma-interferon-inducible lysosomal thiol reductase
- IGFL3: encoding protein IGF like family member 3
- KRTDAP: encoding protein Keratinocyte differentiation-associated protein
- LENG9: encoding protein Leukocyte Receptor Cluster Member 9 (LENG 9)
- LIM2: encoding protein Lens fiber membrane intrinsic protein
- LRG1: encoding protein Leucine-rich alpha-2-glycoprotein 1
- LRRC25: encoding protein Leucine rich repeat containing 25
- LSM4: encoding protein U6 snRNA-associated Sm-like protein LSm4
- LSR: encoding protein Lipolysis-stimulated lipoprotein receptor
- LYPD5: encoding protein LY6/PLAUR domain containing 5
- MBOAT7: encoding enzyme Lysophospholipid acyltransferase 7
- MOBKL2A: encoding enzyme Mps one binder kinase activator-like 2A
- MZF1-AS1: encoding protein MZF1 antisense RNA 1
- NCLN: encoding protein Nicalin
- NFKBID: encoding protein Nuclear factor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells inhibitor
- NOSIP: encoding enzyme Nitric oxide synthase-interacting protein
- NWD1: NACHT and WD repeat domain containing 1.
- OLFM2: encoding protein Olfactomedin 2
- OSCAR: encoding protein Osteoclast-associated immunoglobulin-like receptor
- PALM: encoding protein Paralemmin
- PDCD5: encoding protein Programmed cell death protein 5
- PEX11G: peroxisomal biogenesis factor 11 gamma
- PGK1P2: encoding Phosphoglycerate kinase 1, pseudogene 2 protein
- PLIN4: encoding protein Perilipin 4
- PLVAP: encoding protein Plasmalemma vesicle-associated protein
- PRR12: encoding protein Proline-rich 12
- PRR36 (Proline Rich Region 36) encoding protein PRP36 (Proline Rich Protein 36)
- KLK3: The Prostate-specific antigen (PSA)

- PRX: Periaxin
- PTOV1: encoding protein Prostate tumor overexpressed gene 1 protein
- RFPL4A: encoding protein Ret finger protein like 4a
- SBNO2: encoding protein Strawberry notch homolog 2 (Drosophila)
- SEPW1: encoding protein Selenoprotein W
- SFRS14: encoding protein Putative splicing factor, arginine/serine-rich 14
- SFRS16: encoding protein Splicing factor, arginine/serine-rich 16
- SLC5A5: Solute carrier family 5 (sodium iodide symporter), member 5
- STK11: Serine/threonine kinase 11 (Peutz-Jeghers syndrome)
- TBCB: encoding protein Tubulin-folding cofactor B
- TECR: encoding enzyme Trans-2,3-enoyl-CoA reductase
- THOP1: encoding enzyme Thimet oligopeptidase
- TIMM50: encoding enzyme Mitochondrial import inner membrane translocase subunit TIM50
- TIP39: encoding protein Tuberoinfundibular peptide of 39 residues
- TMED1: encoding protein Transmembrane emp24 domain-containing protein 1
- TMEM160: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 160
- TMEM205: encoding protein Transmembrane Protein 205
- UBXN6: encoding protein UBX domain protein 6
- UCA1: a long non-coding RNA Urothelial cancer associated 1
- UPK1A: encoding protein Uroplakin-1a
- USE1: encoding protein Uncharacterized hematopoietic stem/progenitor cells protein MDS032
- ZFP82: encoding protein ZFP82 zinc finger protein
- ZSCAN4: Zinc finger and scan domain containing 4
- ZSCAN18: encoding protein Zinc finger and SCAN domain containing 18
- ZNF112: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 112
- ZNF134: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 134
- ZNF160: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 160
- ZNF180: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 180
- ZNF208: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 208
- ZNF224: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 224
- ZNF225: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 225
- ZNF226: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 226
- ZNF229: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 229
- ZNF257: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 257
- ZNF264: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 264
- ZNF266: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 266
- ZNF274: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 274
- ZNF320: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 320
- ZNF331: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 331
- ZNF347: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 347
- ZNF426: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 426
- ZNF444: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 444
- ZNF665: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 665
- ZNF473: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 473

- ZNF506: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 506
- ZNF507: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 507
- ZNF536: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 536
- ZNF541: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 541
- ZNF557: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 557
- ZNF571: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 571
- ZNF576: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 576
- Zinc finger protein 613: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 613
- ZNF649: Transcriptional suppressor
- ZNF71: encoding protein Endothelial zinc finger protein induced by tumor necrosis factor alpha
- ZNF737: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 737
- ZNF749: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 749
- ZNF676: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 676
- ZNF772: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 772
- ZNF784: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 784
- ZNF8: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 8
- ZNF83: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 83
- ZNF878: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 878
- ZNF880: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 880

Short arm

- CACNA1A: Calcium channel, voltage-dependent, P/Q type, alpha 1A subunit (Familial hemiplegic migraine Type I). Gene map locus 19p13
- COMP: Cartilage oligomeric matrix protein. Gene map locus 19p13.1
- NOTCH3: Notch homolog 3 (*Drosophila*): Gene map locus 19p13.1-p13.2
- GCDH: Glutaryl-Coenzyme A dehydrogenase. Gene map locus 19p13.2
- ZNF121: Zinc finger protein 121. Gene map locus 19p13.2
- BSG: Basigin (Ok blood group)/Extracellular matrix metalloproteinase inducer/CD147. Gene map locus 19p13.3
- ICAM4: Landsteiner and Weiner glycoprotein. Gene map locus 19p13.3
- NRTN: Neurturin, associated with Hirschsprung's disease: Gene locus map 19p13.3
- GTPBP3: GTP binding protein 3 19p13.11
- KLF2: Krüppel-like factor 2, also known as Lung Krüppel-like factor. Gene map locus 19p13.11 OMIM: 602016 (<https://omim.org/entry/602016>)
- FAM32A: family with sequence similarity 32 member A 19q13.11
- DDX39: DExD-box helicase 39. Gene map locus 19p13.12

Long arm

- GAPDHS: glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, spermatogenic 19q13.12
- HAMP: Hepcidin antimicrobial peptide. Gene map locus 19q13.12
- BCKDHA: Branched chain keto acid dehydrogenase E1, alpha polypeptide (maple syrup urine disease). Gene map location 19q13.1-q13.2
- APOE: Apolipoprotein E, gene associated with Alzheimer's disease. Gene map locus 19q13.2
- CIC: Capicua transcriptional repressor. Gene map locus 19q13.2

- **FCGBP**: Fc fragment of IgG binding protein
- **SARS2**: seryl-tRNA synthetase 2, mitochondrial. Gene map locus 19q13.2
- **ATP1A3**: ATPase. Gene map locus 19q13.31
- **DMWD**: DM1 locus, WD repeat containing. Gene map locus 19q13.32
- **PNMA8A**: paraneoplastic Ma antigen family member 8A 19q13.32
- **DMPK**: Dystrophia myotonica-protein kinase. Gene map locus 19q13.32
- **GLTSCR2**: Glioma tumor suppressor candidate region gene 2 protein 19q13.33
- **A1BG**: Plasma glycoprotein, unknown function. Gene map locus 19q13.43
- **LRC**: The Leukocyte Receptor Complex is a family of immunoreceptors expressed predominantly on monocytes and B cells and at lower levels on dendritic cells and natural killer (NK) cells. The **LRC** also includes the **KIR** locus. Gene map locus 19q13.4 OMIM: 604812 (<https://omim.org/entry/604812>)
- **KPTN**: **Kaptin (actin binding protein)** at the tips of stereocilia. Gene map locus 19q13.4
- **FUT1**: The H locus is located on chromosome 19 at 19q13.3. It contains three exons that span more than 5 kb of genomic DNA, and it encodes a fucosyltransferase that produces the H antigen on RBCs
- **FUT2**: The Se locus is located on chromosome 19 at 19q13.3. It contains two exons that span about 25 kb of genomic DNA. The Se locus encodes a specific fucosyltransferase that is expressed in the epithelia of secretory tissues, such as salivary glands, the gastrointestinal tract, and the respiratory tract. The enzyme it encodes catalyzes the production of H antigen.
- **MORT** (Mortal Obligate RNA Transcript, lincRNA): Gene map locus 19q13.43

Diseases and disorders

- Alternating hemiplegia of childhood
- Alzheimer's disease
- CADASIL
- Centronuclear myopathy autosomal dominant form
- Charcot–Marie–Tooth disease
- Congenital hearing loss
- Congenital hypothyroidism
- Donohue syndrome
- Familial hemiplegic migraine
- Glutaric acidemia type 1
- Hemochromatosis
- HUPRA syndrome
- Leber congenital amaurosis
- Maple syrup urine disease
- Multiple epiphyseal dysplasia
- Myotonic dystrophy
- Myotubular myopathy autosomal dominant form
- Oligodendroglioma
- Peutz–Jeghers syndrome
- Prolidase deficiency
- Pseudoachondroplasia
- Spinocerebellar ataxia type 6
- X-linked agammaglobulinemia or Bruton's disease

chromosomes 20

Gene list

- ADA: Adenosine Deaminase (Adenosine Deaminase Deficiency)
- ANDP: encoding protein Activity-dependent neuroprotector homeobox
- AHCY: S-adenosylhomocysteine hydrolase
- APMAP: encoding protein Adipocyte plasma membrane-associated protein
- ARFGEF2: ADP-ribosylation factor guanine nucleotide-exchange factor 2 (brefeldin A-inhibited)
- BCAS1: Breast carcinoma-amplified sequence 1
- BLCAP: Bladder cancer associated protein
- BMP2: Bone Morphogenetic Protein 2 (osteoblast differentiation)
- BPIFA1: encoding protein BPI fold containing family A, member 1

- BPIFA2: encoding protein BPI fold containing family A, member 2
- BPIFA3: encoding protein BPI fold containing family A, member 3
- BPIFA4P: non-coding pseudogene of the BPI fold containing family A, member 4P
- BPIFB1: encoding protein BPI fold containing family B, member 1
- BPIFB2: encoding protein BPI fold containing family B, member 2
- BPIFB3: encoding protein BPI fold containing family B, member 3
- BPIFB4: encoding protein BPI fold containing family B, member 4
- BPIFB5P: non-coding pseudogene of the BPI fold containing family B, member 5P
- BPIFB6: encoding protein BPI fold containing family B, member 6
- BPIFB9P: non-coding pseudogene of the BPI fold containing family B, member 9P
- C20orf27: encoding protein UPF0687 protein C20orf27
- CSRP2BP: encoding protein CSRP2 binding protein
- CST9L: Cystatin-9-like
- CSTL1: Cystatin-like 1
- CTCFL: CCCTC-binding factor-like
- CTNNBL1: Beta-catenin-like protein 1
- DBNDD2: Dysbindin domain-containing protein 2
- DDX27: DEAD box polypeptide 27
- DEFB118, DEFB119, DEFB126, DEFB127, DEFB129: Beta-defensin genes
- DLGAP4: Disks large-associated protein 4
- DNAJC5: Cysteine string protein
- EDEM2: ER degradation-enhancing alpha-mannosidase-like 2
- EDN3: endothelin 3
- ENTPD6: Ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 6
- ESF1: ESF1 nucleolar pre-rRNA processing protein homolog
- FAM210B: encoding protein FAM210B
- FASTKD5: encoding protein FAST kinase domain-containing protein 5 (FASTKD5)
- FITM2: encoding protein Fat storage-inducing transmembrane protein 2
- GZF1: encoding protein GDNF-inducible zinc finger protein 1
- GMEB2: Glucocorticoid modulatory element-binding protein 2
- GNAS1: Gs alpha subunit (membrane G-protein)
- GSS: glutathione synthetase
- HSPA12B: encoding protein Heat shock protein family a (hsp70) member 12b
- ITPA: encoding enzyme Inosine triphosphate pyrophosphatase
- JAG1: jagged 1 (Alagille syndrome)
- JPH2: encoding protein Junctophilin 2
- KIAA1755: encoding protein Kiaa1755
- KIZ: encoding protein Kizuna centrosomal protein
- Kua-UEV:
- L3MBTL: encoding protein Lethal(3)malignant brain tumor-like protein
- LIME1: encoding protein Lck-interacting transmembrane adapter 1
- LZTS3: encoding protein Leucine zipper, putative tumor suppressor family member 3
- MIR124-3: encoding protein MIR124-3
- MIR499A: encoding protein MicroRNA 499a

- MROH8: encoding protein maestro heat like repeat family member 8
- NAPB: encoding protein Beta-soluble NSF attachment protein
- NDUFAF5: encoding protein NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase complex assembly factor 5
- Nnat: encoding protein Neuronatin
- NOL5A: encoding protein Nucleolar protein 56
- NRSN2: encoding protein Neurensin-2
- OCSTAMP: encoding protein Osteoclast stimulatory transmembrane protein
- OTOR: encoding protein Otoraplin
- OXT: encoding protein Oxytocin/neurophysin i prepropeptide
- PANK2: pantothenate kinase 2 (pantothenate kinase-associated neurodegeneration)
- PKIG: encoding protein cAMP-dependent protein kinase inhibitor gamma
- PLAGL2: encoding protein Zinc finger protein PLAGL2
- POLR3F: encoding enzyme DNA-directed RNA polymerase III subunit RPC6
- PRIC285:
- PRNP: prion protein (p27-30) (Creutzfeldt–Jakob disease, Gerstmann-Strausler-Scheinker syndrome, fatal familial insomnia)
- PXMP4: encoding protein Peroxisomal membrane protein 4
- R3HDML: encoding protein R3H domain containing-like
- RTF2: encoding protein RTF2 homolog
- SALL4: sal-like 4 (Drosophila)
- SERINC3: encoding protein Serine incorporator 3
- SHLD1: encoding protein Shieldin complex subunit 1
- SLC17A9: encoding protein Solute carrier family 17 member 9
- SLC2A4RG: encoding protein SLC2A4 regulator
- SLX4IP: encoding protein SLX4 interacting protein
- SNPH: encoding protein Syntaphilin
- SPATA2: encoding protein Spermatogenesis-associated protein 2
- SPEF1: encoding protein Sperm flagellar protein 1
- SRXN1: encoding protein Sulfiredoxin-1
- STAU1: encoding protein Double-stranded RNA-binding protein Staufen homolog 1
- STK35L1: encoding protein STK35L1
- SUN5: encoding protein SUN domain-containing protein 5
- TASP1: encoding enzyme Threonine aspartase 1
- tTG: tissue transglutaminase (auto antigen of Celiac disease)
- TMEPAI: encoding protein Transmembrane prostate androgen-induced protein
- TTPAL: encoding protein Tocopherol (alpha) transfer protein-like
- UCKL1: encoding enzyme Uridine-cytidine kinase-like 1
- UQCC: encoding enzyme Ubiquinol-cytochrome c reductase complex chaperone CBP3 homolog
- VAPB: VAMP (vesicle-associated membrane protein)-associated protein B and C
- YTHDF1: encoding protein YTH domain family, member 1
- ZFP64 encoding protein Zinc finger protein 64 homolog, isoforms 1 and 2
- ZGPAT: encoding protein Zinc finger CCCH-type with G patch domain-containing protein
- ZHX3: encoding protein Zinc fingers and homeoboxes protein 3
- ZNF334: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 334

- ZNF343: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 343
- ZSWIM3: encoding protein Zinc finger SWIM-type containing 3
- ZMYND8: encoding enzyme Protein kinase C-binding protein 1
- ZNF133: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 133

Diseases and disorders

- Albright's hereditary osteodystrophy
- Arterial tortuosity syndrome
- Adenosine deaminase deficiency
- Alagille syndrome
- Galactosialidosis - CTSA
- Maturity onset diabetes of the young type 1
- Neuronal ceroid lipofuscinosis
- Pantothenate kinase-associated neurodegeneration
- Transmissible spongiform encephalopathy (prion diseases)

chromosomes 21

Gene list

- ABCG1: encoding ATP-binding cassette sub-family G member 1
- ADAMTS1 encoding enzyme a disintegrin and metalloproteinase with thrombospondin motifs 1
- ADAMTS5: encoding enzyme a disintegrin and metalloproteinase with thrombospondin motifs 5
- ADARB1: encoding enzyme double-stranded RNA-specific editase 1
- AGPAT3: encoding enzyme 1-acyl-sn-glycerol-3-phosphate acyltransferase gamma
- AIRE: encoding protein autoimmune regulator

- APP: encoding amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein (peptidase nexin-II, Alzheimer disease)^[13]
- ATP5PF: encoding enzyme subunit ATP synthase-coupling factor 6, mitochondrial
- ATP5PO: encoding enzyme subunit ATP synthase subunit O, mitochondrial
- B3GALT5: encoding enzyme beta-1,3-galactosyltransferase 5
- BACE2: encoding enzyme beta-secretase 2
- BACH1: encoding transcription factor transcription regulator protein BACH1
- BRWD1: encoding bromodomain and WD repeat-containing protein 1
- BTG3: encoding protein BTG3
- C21orf58: encoding uncharacterized protein C21orf58
- C21orf62: expressed in tissues of the brain and reproductive organs
- C21orf91: encoding protein EURL homolog
- CBR1: encoding enzyme carbonyl reductase [NADPH] 1
- CBR3: encoding enzyme carbonyl reductase [NADPH] 3
- CBS: encoding enzyme cystathionine-beta-synthase
- CCT8: encoding T-complex protein 1 subunit theta
- CFAP298: encoding cilia- and flagella-associated protein 298
- CHAF1B: encoding chromatin assembly factor 1 subunit B
- CHODL: encoding chondrolectin, a C-type lectin
- CLDN8: encoding protein claudin-8
- CLDN14: encoding protein claudin-14
- CLDN17: encoding protein claudin-17
- CLIC6: encoding chloride intracellular channel protein 6
- COL6A1: encoding alpha-1 chain of collagen VI
- COL6A2: encoding alpha-2 chain of collagen VI
- COL18A1: encoding alpha-1 chain of collagen XVIII
- CRYAA: encoding alpha-crystallin A chain
- CRYZL1: encoding protein crystallin zeta-like 1
- CSTB: encoding protein cystatin-B
- CXADR: encoding protein coxsackievirus and adenovirus receptor
- CYYR1: encoding protein cysteine and tyrosine rich 1
- DIP2A: Disco-interacting protein 2 homolog A
- DNAJC28: encoding protein DnaJ homolog subfamily C member 28
- DNMT3L: encoding protein DNA (cytosine-5)-methyltransferase 3-like
- DOP1B: encoding protein dopey family member 2
- DSCAM: encoding cell adhesion molecule DSCAM
- DYRK1A: dual specificity tyrosine-(Y)-phosphorylation regulated kinase 1A
- ERG: encoding protein transcriptional regulator ERG
- ERVH48-1: encoding protein suppressyn
- ETS2: encoding protein C-ets-2
- FAM3B: encoding protein family with sequence similarity 3 member B
- FRGCA: producing long non-coding RNA FOXM1-regulated, gastric cancer associated
- FTCD: encoding enzyme formimidoyltransferase-cyclodeaminase
- GABPA: encoding GA-binding protein alpha chain
- GART: encoding enzyme trifunctional purine biosynthetic protein adenosine-3

- GATD3A: encoding glutamine amidotransferase-like class 1 domain-containing protein 3A, mitochondrial
- GRIK1: encoding glutamate receptor ionotropic, kainate 1
- H2BC12L: encoding histone H2B type F-S
- HLCS: encoding enzyme holocarboxylase synthetase (biotin-(propionyl-Coenzyme A-carboxylase (ATP-hydrolysing)) ligase)
- HMGN1: encoding non-histone chromosomal protein HMG-14
- HSPA13: encoding heat shock 70 kDa protein 13
- ICOSLG: encoding protein ICOS ligand
- IFNAR1: encoding interferon alpha/beta receptor 1
- IFNAR2: encoding interferon alpha/beta receptor 2
- IFNGR2: encoding interferon gamma receptor 2
- IL10RB: encoding interleukin-10 receptor subunit beta
- ITGB2: encoding protein integrin beta-2
- ITSN1: encoding protein intersectin-1
- JAM2: encoding protein junctional adhesion molecule B
- KCNE1: encoding potassium voltage-gated channel, Isk-related family, member 1
- KCNE2: encoding potassium voltage-gated channel, Isk-related family, member 2
- KCNJ6: encoding G protein-activated inward rectifier potassium channel 2
- KCNJ15: encoding ATP-sensitive inward rectifier potassium channel 15
- LRRC3: encoding leucine-rich repeat-containing protein 3
- LSS: encoding enzyme lanosterol synthase
- LTN1: encoding enzyme E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase listerin
- MAP3K7CL: encoding MAP3K7 C-terminal-like protein
- MCM3AP: encoding germinal-center associated nuclear protein
- MIR155 producing microRNA miR-155
- MIR3648: producing microRNA 3648
- MIS18A: encoding protein Protein Mis18-alpha
- MORC3: encoding MORC family CW-type zinc finger protein 3
- MRAP: encoding melanocortin-2 receptor accessory protein
- MRPL39: encoding 39S ribosomal protein L39, mitochondrial
- MRPS6: encoding 28S ribosomal protein S6, mitochondrial
- MX1: encoding interferon-induced GTP-binding protein Mx1
- MX2: encoding interferon-induced GTP-binding protein Mx2
- N6AMT1: N-6 adenine-specific DNA methyltransferase 1
- NDUFV3: encoding NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] flavoprotein 3, mitochondrial
- NRIP1: nuclear receptor-interacting protein 1
- OLIG1: encoding oligodendrocyte transcription factor 1
- OLIG2: encoding oligodendrocyte transcription factor 2
- PAXBP1: encoding protein GC-rich sequence DNA-binding factor homolog
- PCBP3: encoding poly(rC)-binding protein 3
- PCNT: encoding protein centrosomal pericentrin
- PCP4: encoding calmodulin regulator protein PCP4
- PDE9A: encoding enzyme high affinity cGMP-specific 3',5'-cyclic phosphodiesterase 9A
- PDXK: encoding enzyme Pyridoxal kinase

- **PFKL**: encoding enzyme ATP-dependent 6-phosphofructokinase, liver type
- **PIGP**: encoding phosphatidylinositol *N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase subunit P
- **PKNOX1**: encoding homeobox protein PKNOX1
- **POFUT2**: encoding enzyme GDP-fucose protein O-fucosyltransferase 2
- **PRDM15**: encoding PR domain zinc finger protein 15
- **PRMT2**: encoding enzyme protein arginine N-methyltransferase 2
- **PSMG1**: encoding protein proteasome assembly chaperone 1
- **PTTG1IP**: encoding pituitary tumor-transforming gene 1 protein-interacting protein
- **PWP2**: encoding periodic tryptophan protein 2 homolog
- **RBM11**: encoding protein splicing regulator RBM11
- **RCAN1**: encoding protein calcipressin-1
- **RIPK4**: encoding enzyme receptor-interacting serine/threonine-protein kinase 4
- **RNR4**: RNA, ribosomal 45S cluster 4
- **RRP1**: encoding protein ribosomal RNA processing protein 1 homolog A
- **RRP1B**: encoding protein ribosomal RNA processing 1 homolog B
- **RSPH1**: encoding protein radial spoke head 1 homolog
- **RUNX1**: encoding protein Runt-related transcription factor 1
- **RWDD2B**: encoding protein RWD domain-containing protein 2B
- **S100B**: encoding calcium binding protein
- **SAMSN1**: encoding SAM domain-containing protein SAMSN-1
- **SH3BGR**: encoding SH3 domain-binding glutamic acid-rich protein
- **SIK1**: encoding serine/threonine-protein kinase SIK1
- **SIM2**: encoding protein single-minded homolog 2
- **SLC5A3**: encoding protein sodium/myo-inositol cotransporter
- **SLC19A1**: encoding protein reduced folate transporter
- **SLC37A1**: encoding glucose-6-phosphate exchanger SLC37A1
- **SMIM11**: encoding small integral membrane protein 11
- **SOD1**: encoding enzyme superoxide dismutase 1, soluble (amyotrophic lateral sclerosis 1 (adult))
- **SON**: encoding protein SON
- **SPATC1L**: encoding protein SPATC1L
- **SUMO3**: encoding protein small ubiquitin-related modifier 3
- **SYNJ1**: encoding protein synaptojanin-1
- **TCP10L**: encoding T-complex protein 10A homolog 1
- **TFF1**: encoding protein trefoil factor 1
- **TFF2**: encoding protein trefoil factor 2
- **TFF3**: encoding protein trefoil factor 3
- **TIAM1**: Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor TIAM1
- **TMPRSS2**: encoding enzyme transmembrane protease serine 2
- **TMPRSS3**: encoding enzyme transmembrane protease, serine 3
- **TMPRSS15**: encoding enteropeptidase
- **TPTE**: encoding protein putative tyrosine-protein phosphatase TPTE
- **TRAPPC10**: encoding protein Trafficking protein particle complex subunit 10
- **TRPM2**: encoding protein transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily M member 2
- **TTC3**: encoding protein tetratricopeptide repeat domain 3

- U2AF1: encoding splicing factor U2AF 35 kDa subunit
- UBASH3A: encoding ubiquitin-associated and SH3 domain-containing protein A
- UBE2G2: encoding ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2 G2
- UMODL1-AS1: producing long non-coding RNA
- USP16: encoding enzyme ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase 16
- USP25: encoding enzyme ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase 25
- WDR4: encoding tRNA (guanine-N(7)-)-methyltransferase non-catalytic subunit WDR4
- ZBTB21: encoding zinc finger and BTB domain-containing protein 21

Diseases and disorders

- Acute myeloid leukemia
- Alzheimer's disease
- Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
- Atrial fibrillation, familial
- Autoimmune polyendocrine syndrome type 1
- Basal ganglia calcification
- Bartsocas–Papas syndrome
- Bethlem myopathy
- Closed angle glaucoma
- Cataract
- CHAND syndrome
- Down syndrome
- Epilepsy
- Erondu–Cymet syndrome
- Ewing sarcoma
- Galloway Mowat syndrome
- Glucocorticoid deficiency
- Hepatitis B (susceptibility to)
- Hereditary motor and sensory neuropathy
- Holocarboxylase synthetase deficiency
- Homocystinuria
- Hyperhomocysteinemia
- Hypotrichosis
- Immunodeficiency
- Inflammatory bowel disease
- Intellectual developmental disorder
- Jervell and Lange-Nielsen syndrome
- Keppen–Lubinsky syndrome
- Knobloch syndrome
- Leukocyte adhesion deficiency-1
- Majewski osteodysplastic primordial dwarfism type II (MOPD II, or MOPD2)

chromosomes 22

Gene list

- ADM2: encoding protein ADM2
- APOBEC3B: encoding protein probable DNA dC->dU-editing enzyme APOBEC-3B
- ARFGAP3: encoding protein ADP-ribosylation factor GTPase-activating protein 3

- ASCC2: encoding protein activating signal cointegrator 1 complex subunit 2
- ATF4 (22q13) encoding protein cyclic AMP-dependent transcription factor ATF-4
- BCR (22q11) encoding breakpoint cluster region protein
- CARD10 (22q13) encoding caspase recruitment domain-containing protein 10
- CBX7 (22q13) encoding chromobox protein homolog 7
- CDC42EP1: CDC42 effector protein 1
- CECR1: cat eye syndrome critical region protein 1
- CHEK2 (22q12)
- COMT
- CRELD2: cysteine-rich with EGF-like domain protein 2
- CSDC2: cold shock domain-containing protein D2
- CSNK1E: encoding enzyme casein kinase I isoform epsilon or CK1ε,
- DGCR5: encoding a long non-coding RNA
- DGCR6: DiGeorge syndrome critical region gene 6
- EP300
- EP300-AS1
- EWSR1
- TAF5: family with sequence similarity 19 member A5
- FAM227A: encoding protein FAM227A
- FBLN1
- GTPBP1: GTP-binding protein 1
- HMGXB4: encoding protein HMG-box containing 4
- IFT27: encoding protein intraflagellar transport 27
- IGL@
- IGLJ3 encoding protein immunoglobulin lambda joining 3
- IGLL5: encoding protein immunoglobulin lambda like polypeptide 5
- KIAA0930: encoding uncharacterized protein KIAA0930
- LINC00899 encoding protein long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 899
- MAPK1
- MAPK12
- MCAT: encoding enzyme malonyl CoA-acyl carrier protein transacylase, mitochondrial
- MCM5
- MIF
- MIRLET7BHG: encoding protein MIRLET7B host gene (non-protein coding)
- MKL1
- MMP11
- MN1
- MTP18:
- MYH9
- NF2
- NOL12: encoding protein nucleolar protein 12
- PARVB
- PDGFB
- PI4KA: encoding enzyme phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase alpha

- P4KAP2: pseudogene phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase alpha pseudogene 2
- PISD: encoding enzyme phosphatidylserine decarboxylase proenzyme
- PNPLA3: encoding enzyme patatin-like phospholipase domain-containing protein 3
- PRAME: encoding protein melanoma antigen preferentially expressed in tumors
- RAC2
- RBX1
- RNR5: encoding RNA, ribosomal 45S cluster 5
- RNU12: encoding protein RNA, U12 small nuclear
- RRP7A: encoding protein ribosomal RNA-processing protein 7 homolog A
- RTCB: encoding protein RNA 2',3'-cyclic phosphate and 5'-OH ligase
- RTL6: encoding protein retrotransposon Gag Like 6
- SAMM50: encoding protein sorting and assembly machinery component 50 homolog
- SEPT3: encoding protein neuronal-specific septin-3
- SEPT5
- SHFM3P1:
- SOX10
- SYNGR1: encoding protein synaptogyrin-1
- TBC1D10A: encoding protein TBC1 domain family member 10A
- TEF: encoding protein thyrotroph embryonic factor
- THAP7: encoding protein THAP domain-containing protein 7
- THOC5: encoding protein THO complex subunit 5 homolog
- TRMU: encoding enzyme mitochondrial tRNA-specific 2-thiouridylase 1
- TTC28: encoding protein tetratricopeptide repeat domain 28
- TTL1: encoding enzyme probable tubulin polyglutamylase TTL1
- XRCC6: encoding protein Ku70

Diseases and disorders

- Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
- Breast cancer
- Cat eye syndrome
- Chronic myeloid leukemia
- DiGeorge syndrome
- Desmoplastic small round cell tumor
- 22q11.2 distal deletion syndrome
- 22q13 deletion syndrome or Phelan-McDermid syndrome
- Emanuel syndrome
- Ewing sarcoma
- Focal Segmental Glomerulosclerosis
- Li-Fraumeni syndrome
- Metachromatic leukodystrophy
- Methemoglobinemia
- Neurofibromatosis type 2
- Opitz G/BBB syndrome
- Renal medullary carcinoma
- Rubinstein-Taybi syndrome
- Waardenburg syndrome
- Schizophrenia^[13]

chromosomes X

Gene list

- AD16: encoding Alzheimer disease 16 protein
- AIC: encoding protein AIC
- APOO: encoding protein Apolipoprotein O
- ARMCX6: encoding protein Armadillo repeat containing X-linked 6
- BEX1: encoding protein Brain-expressed X-linked protein 1
- BEX2: encoding protein Brain-expressed X-linked protein 2
- BEX4: encoding protein Brain expressed, X-linked 4
- CCDC120: encoding protein Coiled coil domain containing protein 120
- CCDC22: encoding protein Coiled-coil domain containing 22
- CD99L2: CD99 antigen-like protein 2
- CDR1-AS: encoding protein CDR1 antisense RNA
- CFAP47: encoding protein Cilia and flagella associated protein 47
- CHRDL1: encoding protein Chordin-like 1
- CMTX2 encoding protein Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy, X-linked 2 (recessive)
- CMTX3 encoding protein Charcot-Marie-Tooth neuropathy, X-linked 3 (dominant)
- CT45A5: encoding protein Cancer/testis antigen family 45, member A5
- CT55: encoding protein Cancer/testis antigen 55
- CXorf36: encoding protein hypothetical protein LOC79742

- CXorf57: encoding protein Chromosome X open reading frame 57
- CXorf40A: Chromosome X open reading frame 40
- CXorf49: chromosome X open reading frame 49. encoding protein
- CXorf66: encoding protein Chromosome X Open Reading Frame 66
- CXorf67: encoding protein Uncharacterized protein CXorf67
- DACH2: encoding protein Dachshund homolog 2
- EFHC2: encoding protein EF-hand domain (C-terminal) containing 2
- ERCC6L encoding protein ERCC excision repair 6 like, spindle assembly checkpoint helicase
- F8A1: Factor VIII intron 22 protein
- FAM104B: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 104 member B
- FAM120C: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 120C
- FAM122B: Family with sequence similarity 122 member B
- FAM122C: encoding protein Family with sequence similarity 122C
- FAM127A: CAAX box protein 1
- FAM50A: Family with sequence similarity 50 member A
- FATE1: Fetal and adult testis-expressed transcript protein
- FMR1-AS1: encoding a long non-coding RNA FMR1 antisense RNA 1
- FRMPD3: encoding protein FERM and PDZ domain containing 3
- FRMPD4: encoding protein FERM and PDZ domain containing 4
- FUNDC1: encoding protein FUN14 domain containing 1
- FUNDC2: FUN14 domain-containing protein 2
- GAGE12F: encoding G antigen 12F protein
- GAGE2A: encoding G antigen 2A protein
- GATA1: encoding GATA1 transcription factor
- GNL3L encoding protein G protein nucleolar 3 like
- GPRASP2: G-protein coupled receptor-associated sorting protein 2
- GRIPAP1: encoding protein GRIP1-associated protein 1
- GRDX: encoding protein Graves disease, susceptibility to, X-linked
- HDHD1A: encoding enzyme Haloacid dehalogenase-like hydrolase domain-containing protein 1A
- HS6ST2: encoding protein Heparan sulfate 6-O-sulfotransferase 2
- ITM2A: encoding protein Integral membrane protein 2A
- LAS1L: encoding protein LAS1-like protein
- LINC01420: encoding protein Nucleosome assembly protein 1 like 3
- LOC101059915: encoding *LOC101059915 protein
- MAGEA2: encoding protein Melanoma-associated antigen 2
- MAGEA5: encoding protein Melanoma antigen family A, 5
- MAGEA8: encoding protein Melanoma antigen family A, 8
- MAGED4B: encoding protein Melanoma-associated antigen D4
- MAGT1: encoding protein Magnesium transporter protein 1
- MAGED4: encoding protein MAGE family member D4
- MAP3K15: encoding protein Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 15
- MBNL3: encoding protein Muscleblind-like protein 3
- MBTPS2: encoding enzyme Membrane-bound transcription factor site-2 protease
- MCT-1: encoding protein MCTS1, re-initiation and release factor

- MIR106A: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 106
- MIR222: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 222
- MIR223: encoding protein MicroRNA 223
- MIR361: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 361
- MIR503: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 503
- MIR6087: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 6087
- MIR660: encoding microRNA MicroRNA 660
- MIRLET7F2: encoding protein MicroRNA let-7f-2
- MORF4L2: encoding protein Mortality factor 4-like protein 2
- MOSPD1: encoding protein Motile sperm domain containing 1
- MOSPD2: encoding protein Motile sperm domain containing 2
- NAP1L3: encoding protein Nucleosome assembly protein 1 like 3
- NKRF: encoding protein NF-kappa-B-repressing factor
- NRK: encoding enzyme Nik-related protein kinase
- OTUD5: encoding protein OTU deubiquitinase 5
- PASD1: encoding protein PAS domain-containing protein 1
- PAGE1: encoding protein PAGE family member 1
- PAGE2B: encoding PAGE family member 2B protein
- PBDC1: encoding a protein of unestablished function
- PCYT1B: encoding enzyme Choline-phosphate cytidyltransferase B
- PIN4: encoding enzyme Peptidyl-prolyl cis-trans isomerase NIMA-interacting 4
- PLAC1: encoding protein Placenta-specific protein 1
- PLP2: encoding protein Proteolipid protein 2
- PRR32: encoding protein PRR32
- RPA4: encoding protein Replication protein A 30 kDa subunit
- RPS6KA6: encoding protein Ribosomal protein S6 kinase, 90kDa, polypeptide 6
- RRAGB: encoding protein Ras-related GTP-binding protein B
- RTL3: encoding protein Retrotransposon Gag like 3
- SFRS17A: encoding protein Splicing factor, arginine/serine-rich 17A
- SLC38A5: encoding protein Solute carrier family 38 member 5
- SLITRK2: encoding protein SLIT and NTRK-like protein 2
- SMARCA1: encoding protein Probable global transcription activator SNF2L1
- SMS: encoding enzyme Spermine synthase
- SPANXN1: encoding protein SPANX family member N1
- SPANXN5: encoding protein SPANX family member N5
- SPG16: encoding protein Spastic paraplegia 16 (complicated, X-linked recessive)
- SSR4: encoding protein Translocon-associated protein subunit delta
- TAF7L: encoding protein TATA-box binding protein associated factor 7-like
- TCEAL1: encoding protein Transcription elongation factor A protein-like 1
- TCEAL4: encoding protein Transcription elongation factor A protein-like 4
- TENT5D: encoding protein Terminal nucleotidyltransferase 5D
- TEX11: encoding protein Testis expressed 11
- THOC2: encoding protein THO complex subunit 2
- TMEM29: encoding protein Protein FAM156A

- TMEM47: encoding protein Transmembrane protein 47
- TMLHE: encoding enzyme Trimethyllysine dioxygenase, mitochondrial
- TNMD encoding protein Tenomodulin (also referred to as tendin, myodulin, Tnmd and TeM)
- TRAPPC2P1 encoding protein Trafficking protein particle complex subunit 2
- TREX2: encoding enzyme Three prime repair exonuclease 2
- TRO: encoding protein Trophinin
- TSPYL2: encoding protein Testis-specific Y-encoded-like protein 2
- TTC3P1: encoding protein Tetratricopeptide repeat domain 3 pseudogene 1
- USP51: encoding enzyme Ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase 51
- VSIG1: encoding protein V-set and immunoglobulin domain containing 1
- YIPF6: encoding protein Protein YIPF6
- ZC3H12B: encoding protein ZC3H12B
- ZC4H2: encoding protein ZC4H2 Deficiency
- ZCCHC18: encoding protein Zinc finger CCHC-type containing 18
- ZFP92: encoding protein ZFP92 zinc finger protein
- ZMYM3: encoding protein Zinc finger MYM-type protein 3
- ZNF157: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 157
- ZNF182 encoding protein Zinc finger protein 182
- ZNF275: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 275
- ZNF674: encoding protein Zinc finger protein 674

Diseases and disorders

Adrenoleukodystrophy

Lisch epithelial corneal dystrophy

color vision deficiency

chromosomes-Y

Gene list

Name	X	Note
<u>SRY</u>	<u>SOX3</u>	Sex-determining region. This is the p arm [Yp].
<u>ZFY</u>	<u>ZFX</u>	<u>Zinc finger</u> .
<u>RPS4Y1</u>	<u>RPS4X</u>	Ribosomal protein S4.
<u>AMELY</u>	<u>AMELX</u>	<u>Amelogenin</u> .
<u>TBL1Y</u>	<u>TBL1X</u>	
<u>PCDH11Y</u>	<u>PDCH11X</u>	X-transposed region (XTR) from Xq21, one of two genes. Once dubbed "PAR3" but later refuted
<u>TGIF2LY</u>	<u>TGIF2LX</u>	The other X-transposed gene.
<u>TSPY1</u> , <u>TSPY2</u>	<u>TSPX</u>	Testis-specific protein.
<u>AZFa</u>	(none)	Not a gene. First part of the AZF (Azoospermia factor) region on arm q. Contains the four following genes. X counterparts escape inactivation.
<u>USP9Y</u>	<u>USP9X</u>	Ubiquitin protease.
<u>DDX3Y</u>	<u>DDX3X</u>	Helicase.
<u>UTY</u>	<u>UTX</u>	Histone demethylase.
<u>TB4Y</u>	<u>TB4X</u>	
AZFb	(none)	Second AZF region on arm q. Prone to NAHR [non-allelic homologous recombination] with AZFc. Overlaps with AZFc. Contains three single-copy gene regions and repeats.
<u>CYorf15</u>	<u>CXorf15</u>	
<u>RPS4Y2</u>	<u>RPS4X</u>	Another copy of ribosomal protein S4.
<u>EIF1AY</u>	<u>EIF4AX</u>	
<u>KDM5D</u>	<u>KDM5C</u>	
<u>XKRY</u>	<u>XK (protein)</u>	Found in the "yellow" amplicon.
<u>HSFY1</u> , <u>HSFY2</u>	<u>HSFX1</u> , <u>HSFX2</u>	Found in the "blue" amplicon.
<u>PRY</u> , <u>PRY2</u>		Found in the "blue" amplicon. Identified by similarity to <u>PTPN13</u> (Chr. 4).
<u>RBM1A1</u>	<u>RBM1A</u>	Large number of copies. Part of an <u>RBM gene family</u> of RNA recognition motif (RRM) proteins.
AZFc	(none)	Final (distal) part of the AZF. Multiple palindromes.
<u>DAZ1</u> , <u>DAZ2</u> , <u>DAZ3</u> , <u>DAZ4</u>		RRM genes in two palindromic clusters. <u>BOLL</u> and <u>DAZLA</u> are autosomal homologs.
<u>CDY1</u> , <u>CDY2</u>		CDY1 is actually two identical copies. CDY2 is two closely related copies in palindrome P5. Probably derived from autosomal <u>CDYL</u> .
<u>VCY1</u> , <u>VCY2</u>	<u>VCX1</u> through 3	Three copies of <u>VCX2</u> (BPY2). Part of the <u>VCX/VCY</u> family. The two copies of BPY1 are instead in Yq11.221/AZFa.